

**D5.2 Strategic Roadmaps for
the implementation and
support of territorial RRI
through multi-stakeholder
engagement within S3 priorities**

Deliverable description

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Authors:

Marzia Mazzonetto, Maïté Debry, Fabien Lambert - BE participation asbl

Ignace Adant, Joaquin Landazuri Benitez - ELI-UCLouvain

Jérémy Levin, Cédric Verstraete - Innoviris

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Reviewers: Marzia Mazzonetto, Maïté Debry, Fabien Lambert - BE participation asbl

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Summary

The primary goal of TRANSFORM for the Brussels Capital Region is to assist Innoviris, the regional partner, in enhancing the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) components of its Research and Innovation (R&I) governance and funding mechanisms, beyond Innoviris' existing co-creation and citizen engagement initiatives. This document outlines the cluster activities in the Brussels Capital Region during the second half of the project. Between M15 and M34, the cluster's work focused on designing and executing multi-stakeholder engagement processes using a design thinking approach to meet the region's needs. Three TRANSFORM pilots, in which Innoviris experimented with quadruple-helix (4H) engagement, were conducted in contexts where no similar processes had been implemented previously. The pre-pilot, "AquaSens," relates to intelligent sensors for water quality analysis. The other two pilots are related to food insecurity and are called "Unsold Food" and "Algorella." The first section presents the main objectives of the pilots, the social concerns addressed, potential innovations, methodologies, and specific features. Then, the outcomes of each multi-stakeholder engagement process are thoroughly explained. Lastly, we provide pertinent conclusions emerging from these activities at the policy and process levels and present significant recommendations for executing comparable processes.

1. Introduction

The core objective of TRANSFORM for the Brussels Capital Region is to support the regional partner Innoviris in strengthening RRI components within its R&I governance and funding, beyond Innoviris dedicated silos where co-creation and citizen engagement are already supported or take place spontaneously. This is in line with the European Commission Open Science requirements within Horizon Europe¹ and Missions² for instance.

To this end, various activities have been carried out during the first 15 months of the project (see deliverable D5.1), with two complementary objectives. The first one is to identify regional needs that could be addressed through TRANSFORM pilot activities. The second one is to understand how efficiently integrate stakeholders' needs and ideas into the public governance of R&I, to meet these needs and increase the impacts and societal uptake of R&I.

There are two types of needs that have been identified. The first ones are presented as those expressed by the stakeholders in the region related to societal challenges that can be answered by the strengths of the Brussels R&I ecosystem. For example, 'personalized and integrated health & care' is identified as a 'Strategic Innovation Domains'. The second type of needs relate to how to answer to priority areas for innovation. A first key need identified is strengthening Innoviris' quadruple-helix participatory processes towards the identification and definition of R&I (and therefore S3) priorities, as well as the way such priorities are addressed through R&I support actions that are typical of a RFO (Research Funding Organisation). A second one is supporting the RFO in identifying agile processes that it can use to achieve a better understanding of its R&I ecosystem, moving beyond typical R&I actors such as universities and private companies. Involving citizens and civil society organizations through sound participatory processes also allows to identify potential unforeseen (societal) impacts of R&I, while achieving better solutions and stronger commitment of all actors involved.

¹ The EU's Open Science policy, available at https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

² EU Missions & citizen engagement activities, available at https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/eu-missions-citizen-engagement-activities_en

Between M15 and M34, three TRANSFORM pilots have directly involved Innoviris in experimenting with quadruple-helix (4H) engagement in contexts and processes related to R&I which Innoviris considers potentially interesting, but where no similar processes have ever been conducted so far. The pre-pilot is “AquaSens” and relates to smart sensors for water quality analysis. The two others pilots are related to food and are labelled “Unsold food” and “Algorella”.

All three pilots have focused on introducing typical RRI processes into existing innovations processes that are taking shape within and outside of academic contexts through 4H multi-stakeholder engagement. The innovators involved in all three pilots, whether they are academic researchers or citizens, would not have had the opportunity to benefit from 4H multi-stakeholder engagement if they had not been involved in the pilots. Despite the fact that several of these innovations benefit from or could potentially benefit from R&I public funding mechanisms and are in line with local S3 objectives.

In the rest of the document, we present the activities that took place in each pilot and their results. All the pilots were designed using the same methodological framework but with some implementation differences. For this reason we present each pilot in a different section, where we explain the details each experimental setup and the results.

The document is organized as follows. The first section reminds the reader with the context of the region where needs are identified and original processes for multi-stakeholder engagement take place (related to water and food insecurity). Choice of pilots is explained, that directly relates to two different but articulated dynamics needed to support RRI.

In the following sections (3,4 and 5) each of the pilots is presented: first “AquaSense” (related to water) than “Unsold food” and “Algorella” (related to food insecurity). Each section describes in detail the main goals, the innovation, the methodology and its specificities, the results and how are these results supporting territorial RRI. The last two sections present relevant conclusions emerging from these activities. Section 5 at policy level, where the link with S3 and territorial RRI in Brussels and section 6 at a rather process level; where important recommendations for the implementation of similar process are laid out.

2. Methodology

“Building the governance and the organisational aspects of participatory processes linked to policy-making, is a very interesting innovation in itself that meets some needs at the level of the Brussels region. (...) It requires policy-making to be ambitious, realistic, inclusive, convincing for the population and engaging a maximum of actors concerned” (a member of the TRANSFORM Brussels Advisory Board).

2.1. Key elements of 4H multi-stakeholder engagement processes

The aim of the pilots was to support “researchers and innovators who will implement innovative ideas to address selected challenges, built on a process of high societal engagement, inclusiveness and openness”. This aim has been accomplished through the three pilots, where academic researchers and citizen innovators have been involved in (open and inclusive) multi-stakeholder engagement processes involving citizens. The pilots have also allowed the Brussels cluster to achieve the core objective of the TRANSFORM project, that is to integrate an RRI approach within existing regional innovation processes connected to regional R&I key programmes. The pilots will inform Innoviris’ future governance of R&I and they will be shared by Innoviris with other Brussels-capital public agencies to further disseminate such types of RRI approaches.

More in particular, in the AcquaSens and Algorella pilots, multi-stakeholder engagement, especially involving citizens, is a process that normally does not happen for innovations which are produced within an academic (or start-up) environment and therefore potential societal impacts are never assessed. It is also key for an innovation to assess whether it addresses societal needs. Most of the regional funding and support provided by local R&I funding agencies like Innoviris do not require nor support researchers and innovators to perform such type of RRI activities. It has therefore been key for researchers and innovators of the AcquaSens and Algorella process to have the opportunity to be involved in multi-stakeholder engagement activities. In both cases, the researchers have been accompanied by RRI experts throughout the process and invited to reflect upon what they were learning step by step. Innoviris is planning how to integrate such types of multi-stakeholder engagement processes in the future, within R&I projects it supports.

The management of unsold food in Brussels is particularly challenging, due to the appearance of private initiatives (such as the TooGoodToGo app) that have had a negative impact on non-for-profit associations that have been active in the field since many years, and function mostly on a voluntary basis. Recently, the Brussels region has financed an innovation (a new app) that had an even stronger impact on the field, generating huge conflicts between local actors. The unsold food pilot has brought together local actors in the middle of a particularly challenging and conflicting situation, showing how multi-stakeholder engagement can be key to identifying common ground and common solutions, assess impacts and provide public funders with an understanding of a complex ecosystem which should be key to support the right innovations in the field. Further Brussels-Capital regional public agencies, beyond Innoviris, have taken part in the process and will make use of what they have learnt to foster similar processes in the R&I they support, with the aim to avoid similar adverse impacts in the future (“RRI by design”). Additionally, evaluation feedback collected from all stakeholders that have been involved in the process has been very positive, including the fact that most participants have affirmed having learned something new and having appreciated finding out about points of view of other participants.

2.2 Connections with D5.1: how pilots were planned to address identified challenges

As reported in D5.1, a series of activities carried out in the first 15 months of the project led to the identification of regional needs to be addressed through TRANSFORM pilot activities. In line with TRANSFORM core objectives, the aim of such activities has been to support the regional partner Innoviris to strengthen RRI components such as citizen engagement within its governance (and funding) of R&I. A thorough work has been carried out (also described in D5.1) to understand how TRANSFORM pilots could contribute to efficiently better integrate stakeholders’ needs and ideas into the public governance of R&I to meet such needs and increase the impact and societal uptake of current and future R&I outcomes.

The following key needs have been addressed through the pilots, which have been carried out between M15 and M34:

- 1) strengthening Innoviris’ quadruple-helix participatory processes towards the identification and definition of R&I (and therefore S3) priorities, as well as the way

such priorities are addressed through R&I support actions that are typical of a RFO (Research Funding Organisation).

- 2) Supporting the RFO in identifying agile processes that it can use to achieve a better understanding of its R&I ecosystem, moving beyond typical R&I actors such as universities and private companies. Involving citizens and civil society organizations through sound participatory processes also allows to identify potential unforeseen (societal) impacts of R&I, while achieving better solutions and stronger commitment of all actors involved.
- 3) Mainstreaming RRI within the RFO beyond dedicated silos where co-creation and citizen engagement are already allowed and supported to take place, or spontaneously take place despite not being specifically required. This is a key objective of the TRANSFORM project, as well as a process strongly supported by the European Commission - for example, through its Open Science requirements within Horizon Europe³ and Missions⁴.

How these needs have been addressed through TRANSFORM pilots:

The three TRANSFORM pilots (the pre-pilot “AquaSens” and the two pilots “Unsold food” and “Algorella”) have directly involved Innoviris in experimenting with quadruple-helix (4H) engagement in contexts and processes related to R&I which Innoviris considers potentially interesting, but where no similar processes have ever been conducted so far. To do so, all pilots have focused on introducing typical RRI processes within already existing innovations taking shape inside and outside academic contexts, through 4H multi-stakeholder engagement. Typically, the innovators involved in all three pilots (whether they are academic researchers or citizens) would have never had the opportunity to benefit from 4H multi-stakeholder engagement if it wasn’t for their involvement in the pilots, even though several of these innovations benefit from, or could potentially benefit from R&I public funding mechanisms, and are in line with local S3 objectives.

³ The EU’s Open Science policy, available at https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

⁴ EU Missions & citizen engagement activities, available at https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/eu-missions-citizen-engagement-activities_en

While setting up the pilots, Innoviris has also identified a lack of capacity by public funding agencies supporting various types of R&I in the Brussels-Capital region (from social innovation to academic research) to assess the broader impacts of the R&I they fund. This typically happens when the funding of R&I is done in silos and not following RRI approaches, therefore scarcely involving citizens and civil society organisations. A particularly striking example of the adverse impacts of not adopting 4H engagement processes on a regular basis can be found in the Unsold food pilot.

2.3 Regional context

In the Brussels Capital Region, the RIS3 forms the basis of the new Regional Plan for Innovation (PRI 2021-2027). Based on its RIS3, the Region aims, as a priority, to improve the resilience and prosperity of the region's economy (sustainability, quality jobs, well-being of citizens), by contributing to social and ecological transitions through the deployment of innovative solutions in response to priority societal challenges.

By combining global generic challenges and current political priorities, six societal challenges are identified for BCR: 1) climate & energy, 2) optimization of resources, 3) mobility, 4) healthy & sustainable food, 5) health & well-being, 6) participatory & inclusive society.

The intersection of societal challenges and the strengths of the Brussels RDI ecosystem leads to the identification of Strategic Innovation Domains (DIS). To target the forces of Brussels' economy, the RIS3 is structured according to 1 transversal DIS (advanced digital technologies & services) and 5 thematic DIS: i) climate: resilient buildings & infrastructures, ii) optimal use of resources, iii) efficient and sustainable urban flows for inclusive management of urban space, iv) personalized and integrated health & care, v) social innovation, public innovation and social inclusion. These thematic DIS represent opportunities for innovation for the economic development of the BCR, with concrete potential to respond to societal challenges.

The **societal challenge** "Access to healthy and sustainable food" is a major issue in the Brussels-Capital Region. Both the demand for affordable food and societal expectations (sustainability, quality, health) are constantly growing. However, access to quality food is not obvious: one third of Brussels residents have an income below the poverty line and 32,000 people depend on food aid.

The **strategic innovation domain** “Social Innovation, Public Innovation and Social Inclusion” aims to address the challenge of an inclusive and participatory society. It is a question of responding to the challenges posed by inequalities, exclusion and poverty by mobilizing the actors of the quadruple helix and by supporting new forms of innovation, in particular to accentuate the user/customer orientation aspects. This DIS includes social innovation as a response to social, emerging or insufficiently satisfied needs, by integrating – in the development of the innovation – the participation and cooperation of the actors of the territory (beneficiaries, customers, operators, users, citizens) as well as new forms of participatory and inclusive governance.

2.4 The pilots’ selection process

Pilot activities were originally meant to be selected through cascading grants. While at the time of the proposal writing Brussels partners saw cascading grants as an opportunity to support costs of pilot implementation, these turned out to not to be an ideal way to get projects involved. As explained in the answers to questions raised during the additional review process conducted by the EC during the summer 2022, pilot projects have not been selected, but rather have been convinced to take part in TRANSFORM. When pilots were supposed to start, Brussels as well as the rest of Europe was in the middle of a further wave of COVID-19, and all the restrictions that go with it, including lockdowns, mandatory teleworking, etc. Desperation, uncertainty and exhaustion are what best describe the context within which the selection of projects took place. Projects, whether university ones, or citizen-led, affirmed not to be interested in 10k or 20k grants to implement something that they do not normally do (RRI), when they had been struggling for a year and a half to do what they were supposed to do.

When an open call launched from June to September 2022 resulted in zero projects applying to the call for interest, partners BEpart and UCLouvain made use of their own local network of contacts to try and motivate projects to join. Colleagues at UCLouvain reached out to researchers and innovators within the university and its spin-offs, while BEpart reached out to local associations. The three chosen pilots (AquaSens, Algorella and Unsold food) were the only ones that accepted to take part. On several occasions BEpart has also proposed to these three pilots the opportunity to receive funding in the form of grants, receiving negative answers. For example, in the case of the researchers/innovators, they have received very limited funding (or none at all) for the development of their innovations. Similarly, citizen-

led initiatives receive from none to very limited public funding for the immense work of handling unsold food that they do mostly on a voluntary basis. Therefore, receiving funding to perform RRI activities on top of their unfunded daily work is not something interesting or appealing to them. Hence the additional workload for BEpart, as the task of accompanying selected projects to perform RRI has turned into literally implementing every single step of the process for them, as it was the only way to have them on board.

The chosen pilots have allowed the regional partner Innoviris to observe and be part of various types of multi-stakeholder engagement processes (within and outside of the academia), with a strong involvement of citizens. They clearly show how such processes can be supported and further implemented in the future in the definition of regional R&I policies, as well as how beneficial they can be in terms of avoiding adverse impacts of the R&I that the region finances in the context of their regional R&I strategic programmes (like Circular Economy).

2.5. The existing narrative between pilots⁵

The first pilot implemented by the Brussels cluster was initially cataloged as the “pilot of the pilot”. This was a first experience where partners realized the need to implement broader mapping of actors to tackle complex problems (comprising actors of the quadruple helix model of innovation) and the necessity to define working protocols to engage citizens at innovation processes (with a special attention to universities given the innovation belong to university students). This first pilot tackled water issues and results of the “pilot of the pilot” were interesting enough to be considered as a pilot itself.

Following the first pilot experience, Brussels cluster focused on a particular societal challenge: access to healthy and sustainable food. The cluster activities were orchestrated to integrate mapping of quadruple helix actors and support new forms of innovation such as engaging citizens in the innovation process. However, a challenge as such, has shown to be quite complex, with several ways of being interconnected with different issues. This has

⁵ Chapter written by Ignace Adant and Joaquin Landazuri, UCLouvain. The chapter was not reviewed nor assessed by the cluster coordinator in charge of the Deliverable.

increased the level of complexity of the approach to be used and the specificities of the methodology. Which ended up in the division of the work, to cover different aspects.

Therefore, the cluster has addressed this challenge through two different pilots that focused on different aspects of these issue. The pilots were therefore designed to be implemented at macro and micro level, and to complement each other in terms of methodology. A first pilot, related to unsold food, looked at the complex picture of the problem, where most of the actor's articulation was mapped. Through the implementation of this pilot each of the quadruple helix actors learnt, progressively, about others actors' perspectives and how are they connected with the problem. This pilot visualized the network, the problem and generated some recommendations on how to approach such situation. The second pilot, on the other hand, went at a micro level to focused on circular food and didn't focus on the network nor the general problem but on the specific link between two actors: researchers/innovators and citizens. Additionally, this pilot generated protocols for citizens to be integrated in innovation processes at university. So, the articulation between both pilots, shows complementarity in terms of the methodology. Where, in order to tackle a complex problem, the methodology should go from the mapping of a problem at a macro level to the working out of an innovation with citizens at a rather micro level, without losing the link with the general problem.

3. Actions

A) *The AquaSens pilot*

This section describes the first pilot activity that took place from March to September 2021. It consisted of carrying out a multi-stakeholder engagement process around a technological innovation in the field of bio sensors, called AquaSens.

The AquaSens pilot represented a “pilot of the pilots”, in the sense that it allowed Brussels cluster partners to test the pilots’ approach ahead of scaling it up to bigger pilots, while already addressing key identified needs. The pilot consisted of three phases:

- 1) A first round of multistakeholder engagement, involving the UCLouvain researchers (innovators) who have created the AquaSens innovation, and experts in various scientific and economic fields connected to the innovation (workshop 1), and representatives of local civil society associations active in the field of circular economy (workshop 2). These two workshops (held in March 2021) have represented an opportunity to both harness ideas and reflections around the innovation from various types of stakeholders, while at the same time collecting feedback from participants on the process itself and the methodological approach implemented. Innoviris did not take part in these activities due to lack of personnel.
- 2) A second round of multistakeholder engagement, involving a group of Brussels citizens in two online hybrid focus groups, dedicated to assessing their needs and barriers around their consumption of water, as well as their ideas of innovations which could be impactful in the sector. The workshops took place (online) in June 2021. Both the researchers and one representative from Innoviris were involved in the workshops as observers; the researchers presented their innovation to participants. What has emerged from these workshops represents a great starting point for several potential reflections and actions around the topic of water consumption in Brussels, its management, and mostly, interesting ideas R&I calls and R&I support actions in the field.
- 3) A third phase of internal analysis and reflections, performed by the cluster partners, to both assess what emerged from the workshops, and translate it in useful

reflections for the researchers, but mostly for Innoviris, as the key target of all cluster activities.

The innovation at the center of the pilot: AquaSens

AquaSens is a technological innovation in the field of bio sensors aiming at improving access to water quality information. The innovation is called AquaSens and it consists in a water sensor that is made out of paper, and that is able to rapidly identify water characteristics such as the presence of certain pathogens.

AquaSens started as an answer to the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) number 6: clean water and sanitation, with a focus on waste water in developed countries and tap water in developing countries. Two UCLouvain students, under the lead of one professor, have been developing a solution for this SDG in an innovative way. One of them through his PhD and the other one through her master thesis project.

Their work has developed a paper-based sensor that is able to detect bacteria and other viruses in water, such as E. Coli and Legionella. The fact that the sensor is paper-based implies that the innovation incorporates some important features such a bio material that can easily enter a circular bioeconomy circuit. Plus, being paper based also implies it is affordable, which can have important socio-economic impacts in society. The sensor leverages on the papers porosity to capture electrodes for pathogen's detection.

Besides providing with a sustainable, portable and affordable way to measure water quality, the knowledge generated by the innovation has important implications for monitoring in different arenas. First, for health and sanitation, through pathogen screening AquaSens can ensure water security and empower communities in relation to water management. Second, for industrial effluents and agricultural systems, through its diagnostics the innovation can help inform about water recycling environments.

Moreover, one of the students was awarded in March 2021 with the “Prix Ingénieurs sans frontières – Ingénieurs citoyens” which recognizes the work carried out by engineering students supporting the development or adaptation of technologies to meet sustainable development principles. Her work incorporates the interest to prototype the sensors following some principals of responsible design. This has paved the way to convincing the students of the interest of engaging in a multi-stakeholder engagement process around their innovation

Citizen engagement process

Of all RRI components, citizen engagement is key in the TRANSFORM project. Within the broader multi-stakeholder engagement process, it is therefore important to focus on what has emerged from the two workshops with citizens. As mentioned above, this TRANSFORM pilot has allowed the innovators to interact with citizens around several aspects and potential uses of their innovation. This is a process that normally does not happen for innovations which are produced within an academic (or start-up) environment and therefore not only potential societal impacts are usually never considered, but also innovations are shaped without taking into account the needs and points of views of the citizens, who will often be the end users of such innovations.

Two focus groups have been held online in June 2021; both the researchers of the AquaSens innovation and a representative of Innoviris were present. The structure of the focus groups was inspired by the EU-funded VOICES project, as explained in the following chapter. The key objective of the two focus groups was to start by assessing unbiased citizens views on their various types of consumption of tap water (and its origin), and challenges they might face, followed by an idea-generation phase, where citizens were asked first to think of innovations which might have an impact on their water consumption, then to share ideas around possible usages of the AquaSens innovation, and its impact on their daily life.

The pilot aimed at showcasing how the responsible development of an innovation (i.e. making sure it addresses societal needs) can be fostered through quick and agile multistakeholder engagement processes, which ideally bring an added value to all actors involved. The aim of the workshops, and particularly of the citizen engagement ones, was not to identify potential solutions nor to perform a consumer assessment of a potential innovation generating in a university, which would be out of scope within TRANSFORM.

The two workshops involved 12 participants, with the aim to have a broad representation of the various municipalities of Brussels-Capital region, different types of living conditions, household size, age, gender and education level. Particular attention was dedicated to inclusion and making it possible for participants from typically excluded parts of the population to take part. Here are the demographic characteristics of the group of citizens involved:

- from 8 municipalities in Brussels (1000, 1030, 1050, 1070, 1083, 1090, 1120, 1200, 1210)

- a majority live in an apartment (9 of them) and a minority in a house with 2 or 3 facades (3 participants)
- in terms of household size of participants, a majority came from a household of 1 person (4 participants), or 2 people (4 participants), one participant. e was from a household of 4 people, one of 5 people and one of 6 people (1 participant).
- in terms of age, there was a wide variety in the group, ranging from 33 to 87 years old: 3 in their thirties, 3 in their 40s, 2 in their 50s, 2 in their 60s and 1 in their 80s.
- gender balance was also present with 7 women and 5 men
- in terms of level of education, 5 participants had pursued short higher education, 6 university studies and 1 post-graduate studies

The AquaSens innovation was presented to participants during the second part of the second workshop, with the specific aim to collect as much unbiased views and ideas as possible around the topic, before focusing on already evolving innovations. A set of infographics specifically produced for the workshop were used to introduce the innovation, such as the example provided below:

Due to the complex situation of the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic crisis, which resulted in having to run all activities online, the cluster leader BE participation asbl, in charge of the multistakeholder engagement process, decided to make use of drawings throughout the workshops. This achieved two aims: to give a “human touch” to the online activity, as it is often much more difficult to get participants engaged and at ease to share personal views in online environments, and to make activities highly inclusive, in the case of participants who might struggle with writing in languages that are not their own. An example of drawings produced during the workshops can be seen below:

Lessons learned from the AquaSens pilot

The AquaSens pilot was successful in proving the added value of the tested multi-stakeholder engagement approach, clearly showing potentially interesting RRI dynamics which could emerge from it. It also allowed the innovators to have the opportunity to discuss several aspects of their innovation with citizens, getting a deeper understanding of whether the innovation addresses social needs around water (and not only), how it might be used (or not used), and what would its impacts be within the broad ecosystem it relates to (i.e. water quality and consumption, water management actors, etc.).

On one side, the citizen engagement workshops allowed to achieve a deeper understanding of challenges and motivations towards the use of tap water in Brussels. This type of information is relevant not only to the involved innovators, but also and more importantly to a R&I funding agency such as Innoviris. Conversations with citizens highlighted how most of them see themselves in a challenging situation where they are perfectly aware that buying bottled water is bad for the environment, but at the same time they don't like nor trust the tap water in several parts of Brussels, due to its (bad) taste and look and feel. This represents a key element of reflection for a RFO such as Innoviris, as it clearly shows that there is amongst citizens a high level of awareness that buying bottled water is bad for the environment and that tap water is safe to drink. Nonetheless, drinking water that has a bad taste and looks bad represents a huge barrier, which cannot be overcome with sensibilization and information campaigns only. As a result, future R&I calls supported by the region could be dedicated to tackle certain aspects of the quality of tap water in the city, involving for example citizens in the definition of shared standards.

The multi stakeholder engagement process also highlighted the need for stronger collaborations between stakeholders and sectors, which is often lacking in the region. Similarly to the European Commission's Science with and for Society calls, and other calls within specific research domains, the regional R&I calls could for example support collaborative processes involving researchers, citizens, but also the private company that manages the water system in Brussels, private companies selling bottled water, and of course concerned public administrations. This type of multistakeholder engagement processes could be supported within ongoing and future public-funded R&I projects (without being limited to the only funding programme that allows for such type of processes, called Co-Create) as a way to create links between evolving scientific knowledge around water issues, emerging innovations and citizens needs and ideas. As mentioned by one participant of the citizens workshops, *"If others are doing it and I can have a say in the things that I think that need to change, I'm more likely to change my behavior"*.

Finally, the process also represented a unique opportunity for innovators such as the two AquaSens students/researchers at UCLouvain to collect views and opinions from a variety of expertise, including citizens' collective intelligence around tap water consumption. They had the opportunity to listen to citizens share views about what they look for in an innovation which could allow them to have access to any type of information about tap water, how they would use it, and more in particular collect reflections on how these citizens see the use of

their innovation in five years from now. This was particularly interesting as most participants said that rather than a usage at household level, they thought that the AquaSens sensors could be beneficial especially at community level, providing information on water quality for example at public fountains or in public spaces. Participants also affirmed that having easy access to scientific information on the quality of the tap water in their houses, such as for example through the sensor, would not necessarily change their water consumption habits, as the issues of water taste and feel are their main barrier. It was unfortunately not possible to further discuss with the two innovators about how such multistakeholder engagement process has impacted their work, nor to share feedback with stakeholders who took part in the engagement process about how their views have been taken into account and received by the researchers. It goes without saying that the AquaSens innovation (or other similar ones) can have further applications beyond the use at household level (such as testing the quality of surface water, the quality of washing water or discharges on industrial sites, the quality of water pumped from isolated wells, etc.) and that it would be interesting to perform further 4H processes involving specific stakeholders that could help better understand and envisage such types of uses. The innovators and their institutions involved in the process are now advancing in their scientific careers, venturing into PhDs or new jobs. The RRI they have learnt through being involved in the TRANSFORM pilot is something that they will carry with them in the future, and hopefully will have an impact on how their innovative ideas evolve.

B) The Unsold Food pilot

This pilot has focused on a key issue for the Brussels region, that of the large quantity of unsold food that is wasted each day, for multiple reasons. The objectives of the pilot were to :

- Highlight the usefulness of involving several key players around the definition of regional policies of research and innovation, especially when they touch upon complex ecosystems where multiple stakeholders are involved;
- Give Innoviris the opportunity to experiment with various forms of participatory processes, multi-stakeholder engagement and knowledge exchange in atypical research and innovation contexts;
- Support Innoviris (and other regional funding agencies) in the long-term uptake of this approach (through institutional changes) by suggesting tools to be used in the

future so that economic transition and scientific research are better oriented towards societal needs and benefit the local actors .

The context: unsold food in the Brussels-Capital region

Several social innovations responding to the problem of unsold food have emerged from citizens' initiatives in Brussels. For example, one of them called [NoJavel!](#) is characterized by three innovative dimensions i) it is created and still supported by citizens who have themselves experienced the problem of food insecurity; ii) it offers healthy and sustainable food aid by redistributing certified organic unsold food and iii) it opts for democratic governance including beneficiaries and volunteers in its decision-making processes.

However, structures responding to precariousness and poverty through the distribution of unsold food are now faced with new players in the field, mostly represented by technological innovations such as "digital applications". Unsold "producers" can now use this new option to sell and dispose of their unsold food.

The conflict between actors has its origin in part in the Region's Be Circular funding programme. Aiming to stimulate the creation of innovative start-ups in the field of the circular economy, this program recently financed a start-up called [Happy Hours Market](#) that allows the general public to buy unsold food collected from several stores and redistributed at the end of the day. Citizen-led social innovation and initiatives in the field have therefore seen their sources of supply of unsold food dry up and, more generally, they fear that this trend towards the commercialization of unsold food will only leave "the unsold of the unsold". available for food aid. It should be noted that no specific funding for unsold food management towards food aid exists in the region. Finally, it should be noted that a mediation process between concerned actors was commissioned by the regional government without success.

The emergence of these new digital innovations promoting the commercialisation of unsold food has led to a multidimensional tension in the ecosystem. Divergences and convergences appear regarding the values of the different types of actors redistributing unsold food, the purpose of their activities, the methods of management of the flow, the target audiences, the resources mobilized and, finally, around the definition and the measurement of their effectiveness.

Methodological approach

In the case of the AquaSens and the Unsold food pilots, the methodological approach used was inspired by the EU-funded VOICES project. VOICES was a groundbreaking consultation process, gathering opinions and ideas about urban waste and innovation from citizens across the EU. Led by the European network of science centres and museums (Ecsite), and coordinated by the Brussels cluster leader Marzia Mazzonetto, VOICES took as its subject matter the topic of 'urban waste as a resource', and the transition to a 'zero waste society'. The results of the VOICES consultation⁶ were integrated into the European Commission's Horizon 2020 calls for research funding in the field of waste management. As such, VOICES represented a model for incorporating citizens' voices into RRI. The results were fed back to policymakers in order to influence the direction of EU research policy. At the heart of the VOICES project was the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). This means engaging the public more in research and innovation (R&I), making R&I more socially responsive and encouraging shared responsibility for R&I agendas, practices and outcomes.

The TRANSFORM pilot made three methodological choices. First, unsold food is analyzed as a flow involving many actors and as a flow where all types of innovations can potentially emerge. Second, Responsible Research and Innovation is implemented here through an inclusive approach which consists of involving stakeholders through participatory workshops divided by stakeholder groups. This is followed by an analysis phase to identify common grounds, and then a multi-stakeholder workshop to present and build on these common elements. Third, the flow of unsold products is analyzed within an innovation ecosystem. This can be defined as "an evolving set of subjects, activities and tools, institutions and relationships relevant to the innovative performance of a subject or set of subjects".

The TRANSFORM pilot has applied the tools of quadruple-helix multistakeholder engagement, sharing of existing knowledge and development of shared visions. These tools are particularly well suited to the analysis of an innovation ecosystem: they bring out perceptions and

⁶ For more information on the methodological approach and outcomes of the VOICES project, see the report "VOICES for Research and Innovation: Engaging citizens to shape EU research policy on urban waste", available at https://www.ecsite.eu/sites/default/files/voices_for_responsible_research_and_innovation_engaging_citizens_to_shape_eu_research_policy_on_urban_waste.pdf

opinions, negative impacts and co-benefits (existing and potential) as well as perspectives (solutions in the form of possible innovations) within the ecosystem.

The approach implemented is designed to be replicable on all types of innovation ecosystems, on different types of innovations as well as on their coexistence within the same ecosystem on the one hand and, on the other hand, to be used not only by regional public agencies responsible for supporting research and innovation (RFOs) but also by other types of public or non-public actors.

The multi-stakeholder engagement process

The phases of the engagement process

The multi-stakeholder engagement process was organised in several phases as follow:

1. Context analysis – November 2021 to February 2022:

This phase was dedicated to the analysis of the context of the flow of unsold food in the Brussels-Capital Region, which has been summarised above.

2. Participatory workshops with selected stakeholders' groups - March to June 2022:

This phase was dedicated to the organisation of focus-groups like workshops involving stakeholder groups separately. Collective intelligence activities were proposed to bring out the strategic elements around the flow of unsold food.

The structure of these workshops allowed to highlight expectations, challenges, and frictions around the flow. Questions asked to the different stakeholder groups focused on collecting general views of participants on the topic of unsold food, exchanges and discussions around the theme of unsold products, individual experiences of unsold food consumption (through apps or social initiatives), the evolution of the sector and possible perspectives,.

The activities organised during this phase included:

- Citizens (beneficiaries/users):
 - Four focus-groups with citizens, users of private apps (Too Good to Go, Phenix, Happy Hours Market) on 4 April, 18 May, 19 May and 24 May.

- Group interviews with customers of a “social grocery” store called ‘Les Capucines’, particularly targeted to disadvantaged publics, on 19 May 2022.
- Intermediate actors between the source of unsold food and the beneficiaries:
 - Non-for-profit actors:
 - A participatory workshop with representatives of associations providing food aid from unsold food on 7 April 2022 with representatives from the following non-for-profit initiatives (ASBLs): [Les Capucines](#), [Banque alimentaire de Bruxelles-Brabant](#), [L’îlot](#), [Les gastrosophes](#), [Cultureghem](#)
 - Private actors: one individual interview with a representative from [Happy Hours Market](#) and one with a representative from [Too Good to Go](#)
 - Public authorities: A interview with [DREAM](#), a platform coordinated by the CPAS of Brussels city (Public Center for Social Action)
- Public authorities:
 - A participatory workshop organised on 26 April 2022, with representatives of public authorities concerned by the flow of unsold food including [Innoviris](#); [Hub Brussels](#); representative from "[Barbara Trachte's office](#), Secretary of State for Economic Transition and Scientific Research "; the [Mayor of Forest](#), one of the 19 Brussels’s districts; a representative of the [Federal Department for the fight against poverty, precariousness and social exclusion](#).
- Retailers: Individual interviews with managers at supermarkets [Färm](#) and [Sequoia](#), selling organic food and products.

3. Analysis / Identification of common ground - June-August 2022:

This phase was dedicated to the analysis of the results to identify possible convergences between the different groups.

The audio recording of each focus group was transcribed word-for-word and analysed. The translated transcripts were coded and analysed using MaxQDA, a programme for qualitative

data analysis. For the analysis of the data, both structured analysis as well as open coding were used. Structured analysis was carried out by using a predesigned coding sheet based on preliminary research. This type of analysis allows for all relevant outcomes to be extracted from the raw data. Open coding runs parallel to the structured analysis and allows for insights unforeseen by preliminary research to emerge.

4. Multi-stakeholder workshop - 4 October 2022:

Following the analysis, a multi-stakeholder workshop was organised on 4 October. It included the following activities:

- Presentation of the common elements identified in the first round of participatory activities involving all the actors of the flow
- Sharing and reflections around a very first draft of shared ideas and solutions (and their impacts) which have emerged from the first round of participatory activities
- Discussions to imagine ways to improve the performance and sustainability of social and technological innovations within the ecosystem of the flow of unsold food
- Discussion with all stakeholders about the process, and its potential use in future similar contexts.

At the beginning of each activity, all participants were asked to sign an informed consent form providing information on the topic and aims. It was explained that participation was voluntary, and participants were free to withdraw at any time, without giving reason. The form obtained participants' approval for audio and videorecording, for the use of the resulting data for research purposes, including the use of anonymous quotes, and for data storage for five years. All data were processed anonymously.

In total, the pilot involved more than 75 persons:

- 50 citizens (“users”),
- 6 representatives of local and regional public authorities and funding bodies,
- more than 15 representatives of local associations (non-profit),
- innovation representatives,
- representatives of retailers and supermarkets and the private sector,

- circular economy experts.

Through collaboration with citizen-led initiatives, whether non-for-profit or for-profit, the pilot has allowed to bring together stakeholders active on a common resource (that of unsold food) and often in conflict with each other. The pilot has involved several civil society organizations, start-ups, big companies, and public authorities.

Analysis of process outcomes

1. In-depth knowledge of unsold food issues

Users are well informed of the wide variety of sources of unsold food that exist today, and the variety of initiatives that support them. The fact that they use an app to buy unsold food at reduced prices does not mean that they are unaware of the existence of local associations and other initiatives. When asked about their knowledge of the sources of unsold food in the region, a large variety of answers was shared:

"All shops, bakeries, pastry shops, butchers, all shops specializing in food" (FG, citizen)

"Local producers. Production plants, food industry" (FG, citizen)

"I can give an example: food factories. I know that a lot of prepared meals that we often recover from unsold items are made by caterers, by food production factories and this is one of the places where there is the most waste that I know of. I worked in there, I never saw that." (FG, citizen)

2. Different types (and perceptions) of "needs"

App users say they are aware that by buying unsold food, they are reducing the quantity (and quality) of food given to people who need it more than they do.

"If this stuff didn't exist, they would have to start donating to other charities and maybe some nursing homes. It has positives and negatives. (...) I did it at first out of good conscience, I said to myself 'there will be less waste, this meat that we are going to throw away', and then it also suits me well because when I am tired, I'm very happy to have my small meal that I paid 6 or 8 € and that I didn't have to prepare. But it's not innocent, it's still money. And if it did not exist, it could be given free of charge to certain associations which need it much more." (FG, citizen)

However, several app users claim that their diet would be very different if these apps did not exist. For example, they would not be able to buy organic food, fish or meat on a regular basis. Some have low incomes but are not in the (perceived) conditions to access food aid.

“For the same price, eating better quality products, clearly. So the quality. For example, with Happy Hours Market, I eat a lot more fish than before. Or the last time there were lamb chops, and I never tell myself, when I go shopping, if it wasn't Happy Hours Market, I buy myself some chops. Clearly, at -50% automatically. Often it is also organic. And then my third point, discovering foods that I would never have imagined buying before.” (FG, citizen)

3. Donation VS business

Several ethical considerations around profit-making initiatives related to unsold food were made. Making financial profits with unsold food is, on many occasions, mentioned as something questionable from an ethical and moral point of view by citizens.

“There are more and more private companies that are getting into the unsold market and then making a profit on it can raise ethical and moral questions”. (FG, citizen)

At the same time, the idea that private initiatives generate employment and ensure the sustainability of innovators' ideas is appreciated by users, as well as by public authorities.

“Consuming via this company develops it, allows people to have a job. So it has a snowball effect and it ultimately allows us to create an economy around that.” (PW, public authority)

4. Transversality is an issue

Unsold food is a hybrid subject. It has both an environmental (food waste) and societal (food aid) aspect. The management of these unsold items is complex for the public authorities. Many participants shared that these unsold food items should be managed by the public authorities, but they do not know exactly by whom. Local initiatives do not have funds dedicated to the management of unsold food. The difficulties of many initiatives in sustaining their activities are also perceived by citizens and other groups of actors.

“This system, it is completely... well (...), it's resourcefulness, it's improvisation, it's true that it's not at all professionalized and we're going to say it's not square, that is obvious.” (IW, supermarket)

“In the social cohesion activities, for example, there are projects where we cook between us for forty people. With that money, we could do other things. I think that more resources should

be given to food aid, even if the national lottery has done it. There are the CPAS and the municipalities that do it, we must not forget that, it is very important. There are many CPAS who now provide food aid.” (PW, public authority)

Users are also aware of this complexity. They buy unsold food because it is good for the planet, but also because it is in their interest. There is a certain awareness that using these apps responds more to an individual need than to the good of society more broadly or to the planet in general. Sometimes it can also lead to over-consumption. The idea that there is a fashion effect in part of the population has been shared at several occasions.

“We are buying more, but there is also the question that in a certain way, for us, it is as if we were validating the industry or the supermarket, the fact that they can continue to buy, produce and overproduce. It's as if we were telling them 'no, it's fine, then we'll take care of it', so we validate this over-consumption a little bit. So we can send the wrong message in fact, by fighting against waste, we are sending the opposite message to the industry, 'it's good, we continue and anyway we will recuperate the rest”. (FG, citizen)

5. Tailor-made services VS anonymity

Both non-profit and private initiatives claim that they provide their users with the most suitable service.

“We generally try to monitor as much as possible, to know our client as much as possible in order to be able to adapt the service to the client's needs, adapt communication, etc. So clearly surveys, whether directly at the point of collection, via mailing, there are also tools like Google Analytics, Facebook Analytics that allow us to describe the profiles of our customers a little. So quite a bit of data that allowed us to draw these conclusions.” (IW, app)

“And of course – and it's going to become even more important – it's a question of budget and I think in this period, we attract more people who use it because it's at a third of the price. I think that gives a bit of an idea of the audience we are reaching. And of course also you have to have a smartphone and the internet, so that probably excludes a part of the population, but that's all I know about users.” (IW, app)

App users particularly appreciate the form of anonymity that using an app gives them.

"Well, I can't go to a food bank and say 'I want the pasta that's there, you give it to me', no, I'm going to pay. In a food bank or CPAS, you have to be in need. So it's not the same thing."
(FG, citizen)

"Another disadvantage perhaps is that if it's cheaper, it's also true that it's not always the good public who receives, if it becomes more trendy, commercial, there are rich people who are also starting to buy it and it will go less to people who really need it." (FG, citizen)

6. Vision of the future

The wish most shared by almost all the actors is that in the future, unsold food no longer exists. Even if it means they will have to pay full price for food, or their local association will no longer be needed. On the contrary, users of the "social grocery" store claim that unsold food is of vital importance to them.

"They don't really know what it's like to have a hard time eating, to have a hard time financially, to have to deprive yourself of things that you shouldn't deprive yourself of. Those who say that there should be no more unsold products, they haven't experienced that, they don't know what it is. Some people who have known the street, like me, I knew the street before being a mother". (IW, citizen).

The ideas shared by the participants have been categorized by domains: policies, communication & education and management & logistics.

In terms of **policies** to implement, the main ideas shared were to:

- Have real public policy for the management of unsold food and the redistribution ('Minister of Food'). Public authorities have a responsibility to coordinate the flow and be clear and transparent about the supply of food aid from unsold food and ensure inclusiveness – but not clear how;
- Review the legislation on use-by dates (DLC) and date of minimum durability (DDM) (among producers and among legislators);
- Fight against unsold items (taxes on unsold items and on overproducers).

"For example in Belgium we have so many ministers, we could create a Minister of Food for example, and it would be a centralized body at the country level. When I mean centralized, I do not mean it is the center that will decide everything but in relation to statistics, at the level

of democratic decisions, mainly at the legal level. The distribution would be done at the level, let's say a bit like a CPAS, maybe -not at the municipal level but perhaps at a higher level. At least each of these authorities or organizations would have a district that allows the distribution of food without the risk of it rotting". (FG, citizen)

In terms of **communication and education** the main ideas shared were to:

- To change the attitudes towards food consumption;
- To ameliorate communication from public actors e.g. a brochure from public actors such as CPAS to provide information on where unsold items can be collected.

"Quite simply, also teach people to cook and value all the products, to cook the carrot tops, the turnip tops, the whole vegetable. I think it's by acting on all that stuff, so it's a lot." (IW, supermarket)

"The CPAS. They don't inform. The CPAS do not inform, the town halls, I think there could be a brochure. There is a brochure, it's just for electricity, "if you have any electricity problems, you can contact the CPAS", I think we find that in almost all the municipalities. That's all, but for the food..." (FG, citizen)

The main ideas shared when discussing **management and logistics** of the unsold food flow were the following:

- To create a platform for the redistribution of unsold food managed without the intention of making profit and accessible to all;
- The importance of inclusiveness (digital divide...);
- The collaboration between public, private, collective citizens, academic.

"Trying to systematize an official circuit for unsold items, so you are Carrefour, if there are unsold items, you have to turn to this person. Create digital platforms, perhaps applications, where any food establishment can register and therefore can resell as it wants at the price it wants to people and force the food industries to produce less or to export more, therefore to conquer new markets in order to avoid waste." (FG, citizen)

" 'We say: We give the floor to young people' but go see in Parliament, there are no young people! So you have to put them to operationalize new ideas with new technologies so that it can happen somewhere. If we depend on the government, I'm sorry, here in Belgium, we will

sit and wait. We cannot rely on them alone. So you have to distribute a little bit, finally they obviously have the authority to make the laws etc., but you have to involve thinking people, new, different people behind it. I think it can also be more spread out, because if we work with the University of Liège, with the University of Paris, with the University of Mons, and they will have these projects that they will distribute in a network, and it can work much faster.” (PW, association).

Lessons learned from the unsold food pilot

The unsold food pilot has brought together local actors in the middle of a particularly challenging and conflicting situation, showing how multi-stakeholder engagement can be key to identifying common ground and common solutions, assess impacts and provide public funders with an understanding of a complex ecosystem which should be key to support the right innovations in the field. Further Brussels-Capital regional public agencies, beyond Innoviris, have taken part in the process and will make use of what they have learned to foster similar processes in the R&I they support, with the aim to avoid similar adverse impacts in the future (“RRI by design”). Additionally, evaluation feedback collected from all stakeholders that have been involved in the process has been very positive, including the fact that most participants have affirmed having learned something new and having appreciated finding out about points of view of other participants.

In terms of challenges encountered to implement the pilot, some types of actors were more difficult to involve. A category of actors playing a key role in the unsold food flow are the retailers, producing a large quantity of these unsold products. BE participation decided to focus on the biggest players among the retailers, the supermarkets. A number of strategies were used to involve supermarkets representatives: contacting press officers and key contact persons at the main supermarkets brands present in the region; involving Comeos, a federation for trade and services in Belgium whose members are active in 20 sectors including retailing; and finally, asking support to the intermediaries (associations and private apps) to get in contact with the supermarkets that are their main suppliers. BE participation received very few answers to the invitations sent to this category of actors. A potential explanation is that these actors are not willing to transparently communicate and share information on their decisions regarding their unsold food management, or that the topic is not perceived as a priority by them.

BE participation also observed a low level of engagement from public authorities in this participatory process, with some key actors missing like the regional agency dealing with environmental issues (Bruxelles-Environnement) or the office of the Minister in charge of Environnement (Cabinet Maron).

Finally, citizens in precarious situation are a difficult stakeholder group to involve. BE participation involved many associations working with this key target group in the participatory process as explained above. Despite the offer to support the associations in the effort to engage their target public, only one association was able to help in the organisation of group discussions with their users. Les Capucines, a social grocery store, invited the facilitators to hold the discussions with their clients at their own premises.

The Unsold food pilot represented an unique opportunity to observe how such type of 4H engagement processes can be a tool for public administrations and RFOs to achieve a better understanding of their ecosystem around critical and multidisciplinary issues. Throughout the process, it has been made very clear to participants that the core aim of the pilot was not to find solutions to the problems related to unsold food in the region, nor to mediate between actors. Nonetheless, the tool has provided a much deeper understanding of the issues at stake, and it has allowed to ultimately bring together stakeholders which would normally refuse to interact between each other. This should represent a starting point for further processes such as:

- The co-development of shared solutions, involving all 4H stakeholders, through the creation of new funding mechanisms that allow for transdisciplinary and the involvement of several actors.
- The identification of needs that can be addressed through R&I support, ideally envisaging ways to address them (through R&I calls) that still allow for multi-stakeholder co-development processes.
- Sharing of the information (ideas, needs and common ground) identified in the unsold food flux with the researchers and innovators performing R&I on topics related to food, food aid, unsold food, waste management, recycling, etc.
- The drafting of policies that take into account the needs expressed by the stakeholders, including references to the implementation of similar processes in other fields and future strategic guidelines for topic-related calls.

C) The *Algorella pilot*⁷

Algorella is a product innovation: a pesto-like condiment that was originally conceived in a yearlong multidisciplinary project for the Master of Bioscience Engineering at UCLouvain. This product embodies scientific knowledge developed at university on the micro-algae Chlorella. Chlorella pyrenoidosa is a unicellular green micro-algae first described in 1890 by a Dutch microbiologist, Martinus Willem Beijerinck. As remind by Vale et al. (2020), micro-algae are microscopic organisms growing in seawater and freshwater; they have short generation time, multiply exponentially under favorable environmental conditions and they perform photosynthesis.

Potential uses of micro-algae are very important (see image below, from Vale et al, 2020) but basic research is still needed. Sanchez et al. (2019) stresses that “Micro-algae were used as food in ancient civilizations such as the Aztecs in Mexico. Aztecs used cultures of *Arthrospira* (*Spirulina*) *maxima*, a Cyanophyceae, to prepare a type of cake named “Tecuitlatl”. Likewise, natives to Chad used the same micro-alga species to prepare a foodstuff named “dihe” (Abalde et al., 1995 in Sanchez et al., 2019). *Nostoc flagelliforme* has been used for food for more than 2000 years in China; such nourishment has been named “fa cai,” which means “vegetal hair” (Gao, 1998, in Sanchez et al. 2019)”.

⁷ This section was written by Ignace Adant and Joaquin Landazuri Benitez (UCLouvain)

Potential uses of microalgae

Chlorella

Source : Miguel A. Vale, António Ferreira, José C.M. Pires, Ana L. Gonçalves, Chapter 17 - CO₂ capture using microalgae, Editor(s): Mohammad Reza Rahimpour, Mohammad Farsi, Mohammad Amin Makarem, Advances in Carbon Capture, Woodhead Publishing, 2020, Pages 381-405.

Figure 1: Different uses of micro-algae (left) and Chlorella (right)

The experimental development aimed at creating an original food product: a condiment and, more precisely, a nut- and Chlorella-based pesto to replace B12 food supplements while using local products and valorizing waste streams of circular circuits. This project was developed under the supervision of two faculty professors, leading researchers in their field and in R&D collaborations between firms and universities.

Figure 2: Agorella, the food, on bread (credit photo: Mathieu Soille)

Because it is rich in vitamin B12, Algorella is ideal for people holding a meat and animal products free diet. Additionally, Algorella is made of disregarded local (by-) products (such as nuts) and the production process uses fatal heat and CO2 from brewery.

The condiment, its packaging and a detailed 360° characterization was presented at the 2021's Food At Work - Ecotrophelia Awards^{8,9}. The Ecotrophelia Awards is a contest for innovative food supported, among others, by the Belgian federation of the food industries. The contest enhances the discussion about the future of food and aims at developing innovative products that are healthy, tasty, sustainable and convenient. Table 2 below presents the keys characteristics of Algorella as it was presented. Algorella won the second place.

Tableau 1: Algorella characterization for Ecotrophelia 2021

Algorella in a nutshell		
Identified market demand/needs		
1. B12 nutrition deficiency faced by vegans, vegetarians and elderly (that can't assimilate B12 easily in their system).		
2. Consumers interested in eating healthy, local and tasty.		
Technical problem		
B12 can only be found in microorganisms that operate in synergy with animal's digestive system. Specially cattle.		
Solution envisioned		
An alternative source of vitamin B12 for vegans and vegetarians than can replace B12 nutrition supplements.	Healthy and locally produced pesto to be used as sauce for pasta, spread on toasts or "aperitive".	
	Production process that replicates synergy to produce B12 using micro algae and microorganism.	
Prototype description		
Composition	34% walnut flour, walnut oil 27%, 7% lemon juice, chlorella 4%, water and garlic.	
	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Main ingredients</td> <td>Chlorella: source of B12 and amino acids (micro algae) Nuts: lipids (very few saturated fatty acids), omega 3 and 6.</td> </tr> </table>	Main ingredients
Main ingredients	Chlorella: source of B12 and amino acids (micro algae) Nuts: lipids (very few saturated fatty acids), omega 3 and 6.	
Characteristics	Local Locally source ingredients (nuts)	
	Circular Nuts: after extraction dough re-use Brewing industry: re-use of CO2 and rinsed water to grow cholera	

⁸ <https://uclouvain.be/fr/etudier/actualites/trois-etudiants-uclouvain-en-sciences-agronomiques-primés-pour-leur-pesto-innovant.html>

⁹ <https://www.fevia.be/fr/presse/les-jeunes-veulent-creer-lalimentation-sans-compromis>

Production	Process	Nuts: harvest, clean, peel, press to extract oil and grind it to flour. Mix flour with water, chlorella, lemon, garlic, salt and pepper.
	Storage	Nuts and chlorella storage at 4 degrees in a closed and dry place. Perishability: 6 months closed and 2 weeks after opened
	Packaging	Aluminum tube – easy to recycle and light protection
	Location	Production: Louvain-la-Neuve Distribution: Brabant Wallon, Namur and Brussels-Capital
	Distribution	FARM, Ekivrac, Bio planète and Bio OK

Additional key characteristics of the innovation

Recurrent tests to generate information about the relevance of the envisioned product and to help identify knowledge gaps

Algorella is an exemplary case of the use of preliminary research results conducted at university (here on micro-algae growth and its potential uses) to develop an innovative product or process. The work of the Algorella team at university integrated up-to-date - but still incomplete - basic and applied research results into a marketable (product) innovation prototype.

The first evaluation of the condiment prototype was made in front of a jury of professors and representatives of the food industry at university. The students, in their role as innovators, were requested to integrate all the scientific knowledge necessary into a multidisciplinary approach and anticipate on every aspects of the innovation up to the legal and marketing ones. It required them to develop their own 360° analysis of the innovation.

After this first test, the innovation underwent another test by the presentation at the Ecotrophelia Awards 2021. This was another test with different representatives of the food industry. In addition to being a particularly rich scientific exercises for students, this innovation contest can also generate information for researchers about the economic and social relevance of products derived from their work.

The positive feedback received at Ecotrophelia Awards 2021 has encouraged further developments in basic and applied research on micro-algae and on the innovation itself within the university. As seen from university's perspective, basic and applied research are still required to develop the knowledge base necessary to support the decision about

launching the product and the respective process developments. Beyond the usual naive representations of research and innovation (R&I) processes, such recurrent tests with prototypes¹⁰ are useful to cope with the inherent R&I uncertainty and to acquire additional observations and information not generated in the routinely process used in the lab or in research consortium. It helps to detect critical knowledge gaps and to learn why such gaps exist and how to avoid them. This is a general characteristics of innovation processes that are punctuated by tests on prototype (and other more or less stable and mature representations of the future system to develop) and returns to the work of producing knowledge in the laboratory and on the environment in which an innovation is inserted.

Figure 3: Algorella positioning – “ (...) not only a vegan pesto, a balanced diet (...)”
(credit photo : Mathieu Soille)

An innovation at the interface of education and research

The second public test is taking place very early in the innovation life-cycle. The graph below represents that position on a simplified life-cycle of a product innovation that starts with

¹⁰ In these tests, knowledge and information with different degrees of maturity are combined and embodied into a more or less refined innovative product or process that is a prototype. We will go back to such dynamics when we will approach Design Thinking, below in the report.

education¹¹ ; at that moment M.A. students, PhD students and their professors are at the interface between education and research.

Figure 4: UCLouvain simplified innovation life cycle at university

Hence, it is providing students with the opportunity to learn more about how ideas, prototypes and innovation can be challenged. Following the nature of the test, learning and competences developed can be very different. Students also integrate research activities and, for some of them, the decision to engage in this professional path and go on with further research and developments. Based on the previous evaluations (jury in the Master and jury at Ecotrophelia) and on discussion with researcher about what is Circular Food, the first diagnosis that emerged regarding the Algorella innovation was the following: a more rigorous analysis is needed on the innovation to address societal needs as a sustainable food option.

Through the pilot, UCLouvain has envisaged to introduce a citizen consultation process at a very early stage in the Algorella innovation life cycle. The pilot has therefore mostly focused on the impact of such type of processes on the research and innovation evolution. As it often happens in this type of processes, the consultation has also had a secondary effect of a learning process, where both citizens and innovators have learnt from each other about certain scientific aspects of the topic.

¹¹ Algorella is an example of the result obtained in a course where students defend a project that requires integrating different scientific knowledge. In parallel, basic research is conducted on key aspects and scientific questions remaining unanswered.

Description of the pilot and methodology used

In September 2021, the UCLouvain TRANSFORM team contacted one of the leading professors and one of the former students of the Algorella Team, who was starting a PhD at that time. Together, they agreed upon a preliminary common characterization of the Algorella products as one envisioned version of the Healthy Circular Food product based on a micro-algae, described in the table below:

Designing Healthy Circular Food			
Algorella Condiment			
The food ...			
... as seen from Nutrition and the Public Health lens			
Key aspects		Expected impact	
source of vitamin B12 for vegans and vegetarians		alternative source for vegans and vegetarians	
amino acids		good amino acid intake essential for proteins	
source of lipids (very few saturated fatty acids), omega 3 and 6.		Good balance between omega 3 and omega 6	
... as seen from a Circular Economy lens			
	Key circular processes involved	Spatial dimension	Type of expected impact
Micro Algae (Chlorella)	Micro-algae are grown relying on : CO2 from the brewing industry, rinse water from the brewing industry	Local, already present, BCR based activities	CO2 capture Fatal heat valorization, less energy consumption
Flour of (wal)nuts	Flour is obtained by grinding the press cake (extraction dough), that is the by-product of the process for nut oil production	Local, already present, BCR gardens and urban agriculture	Valorization of a by-product of local organic oil production

Table 2: Characterization of the innovation by researchers and innovators

The TRANSFORM project was introduced to the Algorella team and it was agreed that conducting a citizen consultation process could lead to potential benefits in research and development processes conducted at university based on:

- their own experiences;

- recent position taken by other leading universities in Europe and;
- key evolutions in the research and innovation organization and governance of firms – universities collaborations on food.

Beyond the scopes of RRI and the TRANSFORM project, the researchers also identified specific interests of a citizen consultation - which are typical of consumer studies approaches - which could potentially:

- lead to potential technical and commercial improvements;
- improve the knowledge about the impacts of the innovation and the key dimensions for evaluation;
- contribute to a better understanding of its social acceptability/contestability.

Researchers from the Earth and Life Institute (UCLouvain) and the UCLouvain TRANSFORM team, worked together on the pilot's implementation design. During the months of October and November 2021, the Algorella team held meetings with UCLouvain's team to characterize the innovation (key components of the multidisciplinary scientific knowledge base and identified knowledge gaps, technical characteristics of the existing product, market potential and strategic positioning). Along these meetings UCLouvain's team also begun drafting the citizen consultation approach making use of Design Thinking, as well as based on the previous experience and workshops carried out within the AquaSens pilot and the overall TRANSFORM methodological approach.

The pilot was designed so that citizens could interact with research and innovation being developed at university. Regarding the engagement of the innovators, they showed their interest to participate in such experience. A recruitment agency was used to recruit citizens based on demographic criteria. The agency was in charge of finding a citizen sample that considers BCR characteristics in terms of: diet, revenue, religion, educational level, municipality, nationality and language. 24 citizens were selected and invited to participate yet, 23 showed up the day of the workshop. This group held the following characteristics:

- 12 municipalities in Brussels (1000, 1050, 1070, 1080, 1081, 1083, 1090, 1150, 1170, 1180, 1190 and 1200)
- 3 vegans and 3 vegetarians.

- Full time employees, students, retired, unemployed and stayed at home parents.
- Level of education ranged: secondary, bachelor, technical and masters.
- In terms of gender: 12 women and 11 men.
- Religion: Judaism, Christianity, Islam, Buddhism and no religion (atheist or agnostic).

An interesting aspect of the methodology is that, while DT processes for innovation normally only involve their market population; the XLAB participants came from different kind of dietary regimes. This implied vegans and vegetarians and non-vegans and non-vegetarians were put together and asked about different aspects of an innovation meant to reduce B12 deficiency. UCLouvain team members suppose that this aspect could lead citizens to think more in terms of societal stakes rather than their own dietary regime. Scientific knowledge was also shared with participants of the XLAB, such as existing uncertainties around the topic and the reasons for such knowledge gaps.

The planning of the citizen consultation was ready in January 2022. Since February 2022, the logistics¹² and some final changes to the process were carried out. On April the 23th, the workshop implementation took place. In May and June 2022, the information of the workshop was processed and, during July and September 2022, main results were laid out.

The process was designed to reach the following objectives:

- to enable innovators to implement a Design Thinking citizen consultation process to assess innovations aiming to meet societal needs;
- to elaborate a report for the actors taking part in the process, discuss this process and create a shared understanding of the results of the process, specifically on the additional knowledge created on the side of the citizens and on the side on the innovators;
- understand the added value of citizen consultation in innovation developments at university (within the field of circular economy) from a RRI perspective.

¹² Including COVID19 follow-up and choices of adequate location for better risk management.

Methodology: Design Thinking and citizen consultation to challenge innovators' views and choices

The Design Thinking (DT) methodology solves innovation challenges through collaborative processes, especially when co-design¹³ is aimed with different stakeholders. Problematisation, alternative solution development and testing and co-creation (improvement) are key steps when co-designing an innovation. UCLouvain extended the canonical DT process to enable citizen consultation in research and innovation activities throughout the life-cycle of the innovation, inside and outside university.

Figure 5: DT adaptation to the Algorella pilot

To distinguish between different processes, these articulated activities - centered on the innovation - are called XLAB¹⁴. It is organized in different sessions or workshops also identifiable by their number (see below Figures 6 and 7). To ease up the experience and the monitoring of the exchange and creation dynamics, sessions are run simultaneously but separately; each session is dedicated to a different DT step and a key aspect for the innovation. It allows for the identification of citizens contributions to each step as well as deeper discussions in each of them. The schedule for the XLAB is presented below, see Figure 6 and 7.

¹³ See for example Pearce B 2020. Design Thinking. td-net toolbox profile (11). Swiss Academies of Arts and Sciences: td-net toolbox for co-producing knowledge. www.transdisciplinarity.ch/toolbox. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3717021

¹⁴ X stands for "experimental" and LAB refers to "laboratory".

Figure 6: Scheme of discussion dimensions at XLAB

10:15	Introduction and indications		
10:45	Alcorella presentation		
	Workshop 1: Problem identification 1 moderator; group of 8	Workshop 2: Solution identification 1 moderator; group of 8	Workshop 3: Variation identification 1 moderator; group of 8
			<i>Tasting Alcorella</i>
12:45	Alcorella presentation		
13:00	Break and degustation		
14:00	Break and degustation		
14:30	Preparation of feedback to innovator (W1)	Preparation of feedback to innovator (W2)	Preparation of feedback to innovator (W3)
16:00	Plenary session: sharing results with innovator: - Exchange 1: what do citizens identified as problems. Report to Innovator and Innoviris - Exchange 2: what do citizens identified as solutions. Report to innovator and Innoviris - Exchange 3: what variation be identified. Report of innovator and Innoviris		
	Closure of the event		

Figure 7: Structure of the one-day XLAB

The XLAB took place on April 23, 2022. It started with a session where all citizens were welcomed and then workshop activities explained. Firstly, citizens were split up in 3 groups (of 8 citizens each) to carry out a specific workshop activity. Workshops were held simultaneously. Each workshop dealt with a different dimension of the innovation and went through a different step of the DT methodology, as seen in the figure above. To ease up the exchanges and get

citizens to know each other, an ice breaking activity was held in all workshops at the beginning. Workshop 1 and 2, were focusing on food and, respectively on:

- the problems to tackle in the Brussels region in the eyes of the participants and their needs and;
- the solutions they are considering or are ready to consider in their daily life.

The innovation was not disclosed to those participants (Workshop 1 and 2). Only after the activity was finished, citizens of Workshop 1 and 2 had a presentation of the innovation together. Workshop 3, on the other hand, had the innovation presentation at the beginning, and a tasting session in the middle of it.

After the three workshops were carried out, participants were invited to a lunch break. During the lunch break, citizens had the opportunity to exchange with other groups participants. After lunch, they were put back together in the original groups, where they prepared a summary of the workshop outcomes about the innovation to provide some feedback. Finally, all the results and experiences were shared in a plenary session.

Workshop 1: Problematization

The first section of the approach is called problematization - following the DT methodology - and it sought to better understand the context of the problem and define the specific need(s) to be addressed. It is inspired in the diverge-converge process of the Double Diamond model of the British Design Council, which comprises the empathy and define DT steps. The workshop was split up in two sessions to cover the empathizing stage during the first one and the defining stage in the second.

Figure 8: DT (empathize and define steps) process seen from Double Diamond perspective

Along the empathizing step, activities to diverge the discussion towards a broad understanding of food consumption in Brussels and its challenges were carried out. These problems were identified through the implementation of a discussion group. The question asked to participants was the following:

What are the main issues concerning food consumption in Brussels?

Participants in the discussion group were provided with materials such as sticky notes, blank sheets and pens, to help them write down their ideas. By the end of the empathize step, a list of problems linked to food consumption in Brussels was generated.

Then, the defining part was implemented using POV method. POV stands for point-of-view and it generates clear problem statements. To do so, participants had to identify their user first. In this case, citizens focused on themselves, as Brussels Capital Region (BCR) citizens. From all the problems described earlier, participants agreed on the most important issues/challenges for each of them.

Notes were taken by observers during the whole session and the session was recorded also. After the workshop was finished, the recording was transcribed so it could be analyzed together with the notes taken by observers.

Workshop 2: Alternative Solution Development

Workshop 2 kicked-off with a defined problem statement: the B12 vitamin deficiency faced by vegans and vegetarians. This stage comprised DT steps of ideation and prototyping.

Similarly to Workshop 1, this workshop split up the session in two. The first one covering DT ideation step (where many ideas were generated in response to the problem statement), followed by a selection of “best ideas” through a defined voting process. The second part was about prototyping the best ideas.

The methodology that was implemented at the ideation stage was brainstorming. This technique leverages on groups collective thinking to generate ideas. Brainstorming can be used for several purposes, ranging from the generation of design solutions to plan empathy work (Plattner, 2018). The session lasted 30 minutes and it was implemented with the help of a whiteboard and post-its. The question asked to citizens was the following:

“Vegetarians and vegans face B12 deficiencies. How can we solve this issue?”

Since B12 is very specific, and there was some uncertainty about how much citizens participating in the workshop knew about it, a short presentation about this deficiency was carried out at the beginning of the session. During 10 minutes, an invited researcher in bioscience engineering of UCLouvain explained B12 deficiency to citizens, including a 5 minutes session of questions and answers.

After solutions were generated in response to the question above, the workshop leveraged on brainstorming again to ask about potential societal impacts of the solutions the group was thinking about. Finally, a process to select them was carried out through post-it voting (where each member got three votes, the idea with most votes won). Once ideas have been generated and selected, participants prototyped the most voted ideas. To do so, they were told to sketch or describe how would they think the different solutions would look like, or how would they implement them.

Like in Workshop 1, note-taking and recording of the session was in place to facilitate the analysis afterwards. In this case, brainstorming exercise was easy to retrieve since the information generated was not only available in the recordings but also in the materials used during the workshop (post-its were used and organized during the session).

Workshop 3: Testing and co-creation

The last stage of analysis was aimed at presenting the innovation to citizens and retrieving their feedback to find ways to improve the envisioned innovation, to generate alternative variations and to identify unforeseen impacts. This last stage could eventually lead to earlier stages of the innovation process. This going back-and-forward feature between steps is at the core of the DT methodology.

The session started with a presentation of the innovation to citizens. It emphasized Algorella's main circular features. Once the presentation was finished, IL/IW/WI tool was implemented. This methodology is implemented by asking citizens to express their thoughts about the innovation by only using the following starting lines: I like (IL), I wish (IW) and what if (WI).

Once circular elements were discussed, participants were invited to taste the product. The innovation being a condiment, taste is a key aspect. After testing the product, a feedback matrix tool was used. This tool consists of drawing quadrants on a whiteboard, where each

quadrant has a different image – a plus sign, delta sign, question mark and light bulb. Each quadrant corresponds to a different feedback dimension:

- plus sign (+): what participants like or find notable about Algorella;
- delta sign (δ): constructive criticism messages;
- question mark (?): questions about the innovation;
- light bulb (💡): new ideas to add/consider

Participants were given 45 minutes during this second part of the workshop to express their thoughts. Notes and recording were taken of the session activities, including written results from IL/IW/WI and feedback matrix.

Figure 9: workshop 3 (credit photo: Mathieu Soille)

Analysis of the citizen consultation process

The Algorella pilot addressed one of the needs emerged in D5.1: the lack (or limited presence) of citizen involvement in research and innovation (R&I) funding processes. It did so by focusing on the university environment, and in particular on Circular Economy and Circular Food Design. Following the citizen consultation workshop, the UCLouvain team members performed a preliminary evaluation of the outcomes and gradually enriched it through the analysis of the exchanges that took place. For workshops 1 and 2, UCLouvain team members developed intermediate conclusions focused on the evaluation of the innovation itself, and the usefulness or added value of the process. As the focus of the pilot is on the university level, it was interesting for UCLouvain team members to assess the impacts of the citizen

consultation process for (i) the university and its role in society and (ii) for the regional innovation system in the BCR within the context of developing the circular economy.

Figure 10 : Articulation of DT implementation at two levels

Workshop 1

In Workshop 1 (session 1 and session 2) participants express their points of view regarding three questions: “what are the main problems around food consumption in Brussels”; “What impacts do participants think these problems have on themselves”; and “what are nutrition deficiencies, experienced either by you or by others”. All conversations were transcribed for the analysis and integrated by notes taken by the facilitators and observers. Answers given to each question were analyzed separately. The analysis focused on both individual citizens responses as well as identifying collective constructions around food issues. Based on the recordings, 464 interactions were identified, as shown in the table below.

	Facilitator	C11	C12	C13	C14	C15	C16	C17	C18	Total
1st Session	117	21	20	27	35	23	54	30	53	380
2nd Session	25	11	2	10	6	2	14	7	7	84

Table 1: Interactions in Workshop 1

During the first session, expression of concerns, issues or problems related to food consumption in Brussels were identified. All these interactions were grouped in 18 broad

categories. Following this, the most voted and/or those considered relevant for the analysis the the UCLouvain team members (i.e. related to the innovation) were picked up.

Cold chain getting broken	Food prices	State of exotic fruits in stores
Duration of vegetables in fridge	Food traceability	Sugar being added in food products and recipes (including for vegans)
Eating healthy and balanced	Food waste	Taste of food at retailers
Eating local and seasonal food products (vegetables and fruits)	Limited vegan and vegetarian options	Uncertainty about how food is managed by food waste apps
Excessive food consumption, including big portions at restaurants	Misinformation about foods expiration dates	Unknown ingredients being added to food products
Food and plastic packaging	Price of vegan food	Vegans & Vegetarians vs Fast Food

Table 2 : Main problems identified by citizens taking part in the Algorella citizen consultation

The darkest green boxes show problems that were mentioned at least 3 times during the interactions; medium-green boxes show problems mentioned 2 times; and light green show problems that were mentioned only once. Citizens expressed a whole set of problems related to food consumption for the region. Among them, eating healthy (and balance), seasonal and local are the most import ones.

After the first session of Workshop 1, citizens were asked to formulate concrete problem statements. They did this by expressing a need or challenge faced and by trying to explain the reasons why they face it. Ahead of the formulation of problem statements, the facilitator specifically asked participants to focus on food deficiencies (and B12 in particular). This introduces a bias effect in the answers provided by participants. Results are presented in the table below.

Problem statements

1) Food Supplements:

"I need food supplements to re-establish the balance due to high cholesterol".

2) Nutrition deficiencies

"I need more sun because I have don't have enough vitamin D".

"I need more vitamin C because I don't eat enough fruits".

"I have a vitamin D deficiency due to lack of products. enriched with it".

"I lack B12 and iron due to difficulties in finding information about meat substitution possibilities".

3) Vegans & Vegetarians

"I need more dishes based on fresh vegetables because there are no options in the market".

"I am missing variety in my diet since groceries at the city center have no vegetarian choices".

Table 3: Problem statements expressed by citizens taking part in the Algorella citizen consultation

UCLouvain team performing the analysis has the following assumptions regarding what emerges from the workshops:

- The analysis regarding the first question shows that, gradually, the participants position themselves in relation to two types of diets and consumption that are categorized here as "affordable food" and "reasoned diet". Given that group of citizens that participated held 1 vegan participant and 1 vegetarian participant, meat consumption was widely discussed, and participants shared their views on it. Another argument, but less used, was: excessive quantities of food ingested, the non-respecting of limits on the ingestion capacity due to portion sizes and the existence of waste (which results in unsold food in stores or food thrown away at home).
- "Position 1", or affordable food/diet, is characterized by citizens having a large consumption of food including meat, trying to find ways to reduce the costs of food. At the same time, they were open to information about other dietary practices/diets and about adapting their diet. "Position 2" participants, or adapted food/diet, put in practice their desire diet/envisioned diets/food choice. According to them, this happens due to: a lack of personalized follow-up; high accessing costs to stores that offer their desire food options and; finding information, which is time and energy consuming.
- According to our analysis, the two groups face the same challenge: stick to their choices (and to what their choices imply), given all the difficulties mentioned above, and making their objective accountable to societal stakes or give up and revert to affordable food.
- There are two identifiable positions derived from the exchanges in the workshop, as shown in the table below. The first one (top left) refers to food in large quantities and at

low cost. The second, a situation where citizens are questioning the quality of what they are ingesting (diet); where they are reducing, or even eliminating, meat consumption and; where they are relying on small local networks linked to lower environmental impacts. The participants took a critical look at the positions they adopt in the discussions, emphasizing the difficulties and problems they encounter and the consequences for them or for their living environment.

- The existence of problems identified by the participants and the possibility of not having these problems resolved by these two positions, in terms of food, could eventually lead to a problematic evolution in their food choices and/or in the system (living environment) in which they are inserted. **These are reasons for questioning or (most often) for dissatisfaction: participants are stressing the reason why it is difficult for them to modify their diet in the desired direction and to reach balances (food, ethical and environmental) between the stakes they mentioned before.**

Figure 11: Interpretation of citizens positions towards food consumption

The figure above represent the instability of choices that participants stress. Three main issues emerge from the exchanges between participants (bottom right of the diagram). In the absence of solutions for these problems, the participants' choices are difficult to maintain and, depending on the case, the participants occasionally or systematically modify their

choice in favor of a more affordable food/diet. These are, depending on the case, reasons for questioning or (most often) dissatisfaction. Participants stressed the difficulty for them to modify their diet in the desired direction and to reach balances (food, ethical and environmental) between the stakes. A way of synthesizing this dynamic is presented below; the instability of food choices between the two positions arise when an individual or a group is not able to overcome problems or tensions created by food choices (grey zone in the figure).

Figure 12: Interpretation of food consumption dynamics based on challenges expressed by participants in the Algorella pilot workshop

Implications for the evaluation of the Algorella innovation

1. Response to needs

According to the UCLouvain team, two questions are key for the evaluation of the innovation: (i) does the innovation respond to a legitimate need clearly identified by the participants and (ii) can we extend this need to a particular need of BCR citizens and in the form of a specific demand.

The UCLouvain team confirms that the innovation is addressing a need identified during the exchanges with the participants. According to the UCLouvain team, analysis of the exchanges showed the need to respond to deficiencies resulting from a dietary imbalance that is difficult to restore due to various reasons. One of the reasons being vegetarian or vegan diets that induces B12 deficiency. The innovator has targeted this group and others who are frequently deficient in B12 (e.g. elderly people). So, according to the UCLouvain team there is

an existing demand to solve this deficiency and the Algorella innovation is an alternative to the current consumption of food supplements.

Some participants mentioned the existence of links between their food choices and their health, their economic situation and environmental problems or ethics. Most of the participants considered environmental issues (CO2 emissions and packaging) and ethical issues (animal welfare) as societal issues that are linked to their food choices. Additionally, the Algorella innovation aims at developing a process to better use and integrate waste stream and/or co-products while tackling B12 deficiency.

During Workshop 1 exchanges, it was not easy for participants to identify potential positive effects on several societal issues:

- choosing foods that have a positive effect on health (or 'less negative effects') requires bearing additional individual costs (additional expenses at the individual level) and that generate collective costs (travel to find food);
- when it is possible to adapt food consumption for ethical and/or environmental reasons (animal welfare and pressure on natural resources through livestock farming), imbalances and deficiencies appear at the individual level (case of B12 deficiency in vegans) could happen.

In other words, it is difficult to restore the (individual) balance on the person's side (balanced diet) while contributing to restore a (collective) balance in their common living environment. The compatibility between these two objectives is said to be difficult to achieve.

As pointed out by the innovator and the documents provided, Algorella is an example of an innovative product that makes these objectives compatible. This innovation allows to solve a nutritional deficiency (i.e. which makes it possible to restore a balance on citizens person health without relying on food supplements) while contributing to a better use of resources and by-products (restoring a balance in his living environment).

The Algorella innovation is exemplary since it manages to articulate the problem of deficiencies (linked to food) with the development of circular economy (or bioeconomy). But the solution in the form of a product innovation is only partial. As mentioned by the innovator himself, it is still needed to develop other products (of this same type) to expand the offer and supply a sufficient variety of options for different type of deficiencies. Complementary, the innovation could explore the development of a platform "Circular Food Design" to valorize

other co-products and bioeconomy waste streams and to design ways to use them in the preparation of foods including microalgae to address B12 deficiencies.

2. Unsatisfied needs

Other needs mentioned by the participants were the management of unsold food and the surplus of not consumed purchased food that is thrown away. These two forms of waste are associated with mass consumption (too much food offered in stores, problematic management of expiry date, quantities too large compared to ingestion capacity, etc.).

Access to information and stores where food is sold is a problem for all participants. The costs to be borne are, according to participants, one of the reasons why it is difficult to modify their diet. In other words, the absence of information makes the identification of foods more difficult and the search for a balance diet more expensive. From this point of view, the innovator does not seek to offer a solution.

The link between food and circular economy addressed by Algorella is one possible response to the identified issues. However, it should be noted that participants did not make the link between the notion of healthy food with the notion of circular economy. They naturally made an association between (i) local food and (ii) the reduction of negative impacts on the environment (the underlying idea here is the reduction of the CO₂ footprint associated with the consumption of seasonal foods and/or from so-called short supply chains). Therefore, Algorella is an example of a product innovation that goes beyond the needs expressed by the participants. This can be used as a warning. Given that the participants stressed the uncertainty faced about processed food products quality, it would be necessary to analyze later the potential evolution of distrust and even future social contestability of the innovation. The simplicity of the product (only a few ingredients with local sourcing) will probably limit distrust of the product (refer to the analyzes of the other workshops). Yet, participants did not have enough time to focus on the issues of the product, such as, using other resources (CO₂ and hot brewery water) and to position themselves in relation to them. For this reason, and at this stage of the process, it is therefore not possible to draw definitive conclusions regarding the response of the demand and distrust/contestability aspects.

Designing healthy circular food requires developing knowledge (research) and embodying it in product or process (innovation) to solve problems citizen are confronted with when facing persistent tensions and disequilibrium impacting their health and the environment. Through solving citizen's problems, more of them are in position to contribute to sustainability while

relying on balanced diet/food/nutrition. The innovation potential is identified at this stage of the workshop, through the eyes of participants in XLAB, before Algorella presentation. In the BCR, an innovation will, under precise conditions, create new value chains where people will rely on balanced diet compatible with the equilibrium in health and environment (HEF); in other words, it will be supporting the transition to another equilibrium (from affordable food to healthy environmental food (HEF)”, see illustration below).

Figure 13 : Transitions in food consumption identified by UCLouvain within the Algorella pilot

According to the UCLouvain team, the analysis shows that Algorella as an innovation will impact more the territory as it is implementing circularity, that is by using of waste and by-products (see illustration below). Algorella is an example of a product innovation that can contribute to an additional change (from HEF to HCF) : to increase circularity in food design and reach a healthy balanced diet without relying on products of dietary supplement industry. This potential could not emerge from citizens’/participants’ contribution because they are not used to combine “healthy food” with “food made from co-products and waste”. Note finally that the analysis of potential impacts shows that this innovation does not answer to the needs of groups of citizens that have no access to affordable food and are prevented to use food waste and that incomplete knowledge still prevails (for example about determinants of deficiency and longevity).

Figure 14: potential Algorella’s role in foods consumption dynamics suggested by UCLouvain

Workshop 2

In workshop 2, citizens were asked to generate ideas and prototypes to solve the problem innovators were trying to tackle, without disclosing any information to citizens about Algorella. The discussion was led following three questions: “how can we tackle B12 deficiencies?” What impacts do these solutions have on societal stakes?” and the third question (focused on the prototype development) “how would these solutions look like/ or be implemented?”.

Solutions proposed by citizens, together with reactions to each other’s propositions, evolution of the ideas generated and the articulation between responses; were considered for the analysis. Same as in Workshop 1, the whole discussion was transcribed and it was complemented with notes taken by facilitators and observers. Responses to each question were analyzed separately. The analysis consisted of reviewing each person contribution, and understanding how were contributions adding to what was collectively constructed (a set of ways to address B12 deficiency and how can these ideas be presented as concreted solutions). Based on the recordings, 304 interactions were clearly identified and considered for analysis during Workshop 2.

Table 4 : Interaction Workshop 2

	Animator	C21	C22	C23	C24	C25	C26	C27	PhD	Total
Workshop 2	89	10	42	22	25	19	43	35	190	304

During the first session, different ideas were generated to address B12 deficiency. All these ideas are listed in the table below. In total, 27 ideas were suggested during the session. Due to some closeness between them and given that some of them were discharged during the

discussion, the facilitator grouped them in different categories. Some of them, such as number 1, integrates many ideas: it comprises the reflection made about conditions in other countries where vegans reach high longevity rates. They raised the question that this fact suggests that there may exist some other conditions that guarantee a long healthy life regardless having a vegan diet; or some conditions that would avoid having a B12 deficiency besides being vegan.

Table 3 : Alternative solutions to address B12 deficiency

How can we address B12 nutrition deficiencies?
1) Studying other lifestyles, body conditions and information
2) Researching and alternative sources (algae, yeast, spirulina, etc.):
3) Extracting microorganism in animals and implant them somewhere else - artificially reproduce them
4) Produce it through genetic modification
5) Functional food and food supplements enriched with B12: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drinks (energy drinks) • Enriched and eatable toothpaste • Candies/sweets • Infusions
6) Vaccines/injections/patches
7) Nasal sprays
8) Limestone filter with B12 distributor

Once the ideas were generated and partially organized, the facilitator asked about potential impacts by reorganizing the ideas in different groups. These results are presented in the table below.

Table 4 : Potential Impacts of Ideas generated

Envisioned solution	Potential impact
Food supplements: vitamins, pills, tablets...	Packing, transportation, consumers price, ways of delivering, over consumption need of raw materials, affordability, related subsidies, reimbursed by health insurance
Candies, toothpaste, patches, nasal spray, infusions, medical follow ups	Waste, costs (including personal to manage information distribution), patent access, energy for distribution and sales, animal welfare, impacts on the Earth
Algae, spirulina	Intensive production and impact on the sea
Microorganisms' implants and genetic modification	Peoples perceptions and other issues like the Covid vaccines have had

Synthesize, imitate B12 vitamin artificially	Ethics
Study every person uniqueness: body conditions, health, impact on the fetus of vegan parents	Cultural and educational impact
Genetic modification, agricultural promotion	Ethics vs politics

To address the B12 deficiency, we can observe a wide range of solutions expressed by citizens. Even though the facilitator tried to group these ideas in different sets of solutions, as seen above, UCLouvain team members have further explained how they see these interconnections and what do these solutions represent for Algorella innovators according to them. According to their interpretation, citizens showed that addressing a problem such as B12 can be done in two different ways. Some of them were more conservative (related to the supplements) and other more original (related to a larger/different potential causality - that is not well known on their side). According to UCLouvain team assumptions, the difference between these two solutions is their knowledge base. The first position is a narrow view of the problem (lineal diet causality): B12 deficiency is caused due to a lack of meat or animal products consumption. In line with this way of understanding the problem, is the solution: the way to address low B12 levels is to introduce food supplements in their diet.

Figure 16 : Lineal view of the problem, according to UCLouvain

The second position tries to break down the knowledge base and questions whether there is a broader explanation, or conditions for having such a deficiency. In other words, it is not only about diet (eating meat or animals' products) but maybe other factors such as lifestyle, culture and body conditions/characteristics. The UCLouvain team idea of enlarging the scope of the knowledge base (and breaking down the linearity way of thinking to understand the problem), and raising the question "what are other determinants of the B12 deficiency?", came after the reflection made by one citizen. She mentioned that yogis in Japan were vegan and they are known for their longevity. She did not explicitly argue that their lifestyle or living conditions would prevent them from having a deficiency, but she built up on the fact that they have a long-lasting (healthy) life. So, she questioned the lineal causality of vegan diet equals a B12 deficiency. Together with this questioning, it also came the proposal to expand the lines of research so that these questions will be resolved.

According to the UCLouvain team, this provides a strong input for their analysis, since it introduces the notion of knowledge exploration. Knowledge exploration is in their view a by-

product of the analysis, that proposes new and complementary lines of research (that may not have been considered earlier by researchers) and that could potentially expand their innovation 360 view. Yet, there is uncertainty of the scientific background sustaining these questions. Consequently, the innovator needs to evaluate their pertinence.

Figure 17 : UCLouvain view of expanding knowledge base through citizen consultation

As seen in the figure above, innovators developed their idea by understanding the problem and the solution in a lineal manner. When we introduce the same question about B12 deficiency to citizens, given their different background (not necessarily scientific), UCLouvain interpretation is that they went backwards in the linear understanding of the problem to question the reasons for this deficiency. It is important to mention that at the beginning of the session they were given a short presentation about B12 deficiencies by a PhD student. Yet, they managed to find a connection between vegans and longevity that would support their questioning of the information given to them. Based on this, they developed a wide range of potential solutions that need complementary research to determine their viability.

These wide range of solutions are not strictly related to food supplements – which can be considered as the conservative/lineal and standard solution – but rely on a wide spectrum of knowledge bases. This means that if the innovation considers valuable to pursue a specific knowledge exploration path, it will require to integrate other disciplines for the understanding of the problem and the development of a new/improved solution.

Implications for the evaluation of the Algorella innovation

1. Viability of food supplement

Based on the UCLouvain interpretations of the replies given by citizen, when their understanding of the problem was lineal (same as innovator), they came up with similar solutions than innovators: enriched foods or drinks. None of them though about a condiment yet, suggestions were made about drinks, candies and toothpaste. To some extent this can validate the innovators way of thinking about the solution: moving from just food supplements towards enriched food that integrates different aspects (such as locally produced ingredients). Nonetheless, circularity or potential positive externalities derived from this solution were excluded from citizens reflection.

2. Implementing knowledge exploration

According to the UCLouvain team, citizens showed their capacity to think “outside the box” and propose several paths for future research – under the aim of better understanding the problem of B12 deficiency. Yet, this implies questioning several aspects where innovators have already been working on, so a detail process needs to be established in order to incorporate this potential research paths into the innovation. We propose incorporating these potential lines of research at two levels:

- innovators need to contrast this information to determine whether the questions raised for knowledge exploration were already considered and explored by them and;
- they need to ask whether there is scientific validity and truthfulness on the question so that it would make the exploration valuable.

3. Enlarging the knowledge base

Such a process has the potential to trigger one question to the innovators: “Is there something missing in your research? Or something that you took it as granted?”. If the innovator confirms this situation, the outcome of engaging on complementary research lines could potentially change the nature of the solution. Moreover, it could potentially reach to less costly solutions, or more effective ways to address societal needs. So, it also represents an incentive for the innovator or the researcher to consider and explore these alternatives.

4. Linking Workshop 1 and 2

According to the UCLouvain team, it is possible to draw a common line between both workshops. Citizen are in both cases expanding the reflection. In Workshop 1 they expanded the specific problem addressed by innovators to understand all the stakes around it and the dynamic of food consumption. In Workshop 2 they proposed expanding the knowledge base to better understand the technical problem and consequently draw new solutions to the

problem. Additionally, by broadening perceptions, issues about sustainability emerge in different forms which may suggest positive impacts on the development of the innovation. Issues such as eating local and healthy emerged as important stakes in workshop 1; whereas in workshop 2, seeing nutrition deficiencies not only related to food supplements but nutrition as a whole.

Workshop 3 and plenary sessions

Workshop 3 recordings showed 929 interactions among the participants that were considered for analysis. These were clear interactions of citizens, Algorella innovator intervention and the animator during the workshop yet, this does not account for unclear statements or when more than two people spoke at the same time.

Table 5 : Interactions Workshop 3

	Animator	C31	C32	C33	C34	C35	C36	C37	C38	Innovator	Total
1 st Session	111	35	22	37	24	77	63	42	50	28	489
2 nd Session	123	29	13	20	12	78	51	72	23	19	440

Workshop 3 focused on citizens feedback. Results below show a comprised summary of what citizens provided as feedback for the Algorella innovation using the feedback matrix. This was built using inputs not only of the matrix itself but results from the first session.

Figure 18 : Feedback matrix Workshop 3

According to the UCLouvain team, the first important finding of this workshop is that, within the framework of Workshop 3, it was difficult for citizens to break the “market research”

mindset: once the innovation is presented it is difficult to think outside the box.¹⁵ The feedback provided by citizens in this set up was mainly related to the product's marketable potential. This limits the scope of Workshop 3 because it was aimed at identifying unforeseen impacts; but in this case the feedback turned towards market validation and potential improvements. These results are valuable for innovators within the framework of a market research perspective but not for a 360° view which was the ultimate goal. Additional protocols are needed to increase the utility of this workshop in terms of impact assessments.

A plenary session took place at the end of the day. It was an opportunity for participants to present their group results (obtained before and modified after the presentation of Aglorella). Based on the observations and transcriptions, we see that it was the opportunity for participants to see that some of them have developed positions and arguments that distance themselves from the product, by questioning a more general problem. The process aimed at having this plenary session to end the exchanges. This was followed by an informal discussions and interviews with certain participants which make it possible to identify various adjustments to be made in the practical organization of the workshop. During these informal discussions, the exchanges relate in particular to knowledge of microanalyses and their nutritional properties (Spirulina versus Chlorella). More generally, it is noted that the properties of micro-algae are little known.

Useful lessons learned towards stronger territorial RRI

1. Useful exploration of the problematization step for the evaluation of an innovation

If well directed, the citizen consultation is not limited to identify problems faced by each participant in a given territory. It actually allows to push the analysis further to obtain two types of results that are particularly useful for the evaluation of an innovation:

- To identify the positions adopted by participants in relation to that problem: to what extent they are concerned, how do they manage it, how do they position themselves in relation to other participants, etc.

¹⁵ Explanatory note from BE participation asbl: it is often the case that when a citizen consultation process is shaped as a market research, which was the case for the Aglorella pilot Workshop 3, it will lead to market research types of outcomes.

- To gain a deeper insight into the relationship between individual perceptions of the effects of personal choices (specifically, health imbalances resulting from food choices) and the associated collective environmental problems related to food consumption that it contributes (can contribute) to solve (reduction of CO₂ emissions associated with the consumption of food via its production and transport) or, on the contrary, that it contributes to create (or maintain).

By analyzing these connections, the innovator can better understand the complex interplay between individual actions and their larger environmental consequences.

The first result is useful because it helps to better understand the population that was targeted by the innovation. Based on this, one can extend the exploration in small groups and with other approaches too, that will make possible to connect with a larger population (by questionnaire for example).

The second result is even more important for the analysis of an innovation that aims at delivering a twofold solution: (i) on the one hand to a food deficiency (to restore a balanced diet) and, (ii) on the other hand to the under-use or the waste of valuable local resources (co-products and waste from the bioeconomy or the economy). The analysis of the exchanges within workshop 1 help to **identify conditions under which individuals would choose options by which they are individually and collectively better off**. The innovation can then be evaluated with this information: **does it contribute to making these objectives (more) compatible?** This is a key question when designing circular food and when trying to evaluate (“ex-ante”) its impacts: from the point of view of the problems identified by citizens, does the innovation make it possible to reach a level of impact (“balanced diet” and “circularity”) that individuals (and society as a whole) do not reach without this innovation. If the answer is positive, this provides key insights about the potential impact of the innovation as seen or as evaluated from the point of view of citizens. It is important to mention that the second result will not be obtained easily.

2. Generalizing to BCR citizens and validation

We started these conclusions with two relevant questions for the innovation: (i) does the innovation answer to a legitimate need, that has been identified in a clear way by the participants and, (ii) that we can relate to a particular need of BCR citizens and that is expressed as a demand by themselves. The responses provided did not address the legitimacy and validity question of Workshop 1 results.

Given the characteristics of our experimental setting for Circular Food, it is premature to conclude about the legitimacy of the identified needs and the validity of the results. Citizens belong to the BCR; therefore, we obtained an overview of problems and needs that could be relevant for the Region. Nevertheless, because of the characteristics of the sample and the exploratory nature of this pilot, one have to be careful with: (i) drawing general conclusions about the nature of problems and needs for all citizens in BCR and (ii) to make a final assessment of the innovation.

3. An exploration to be completed

This exploratory work is insufficient to lead to a successful evaluation of an innovation. But it shows how the protocols, still imperfect here, can be used for this type of evaluation.

The work done in previous workshops will aid in generating solutions for the identified needs and demands. Participants' prior knowledge can be helpful in envisioning solutions. The work carried out in Workshop 2 with citizens will generate bottom-up solutions. To evaluate an innovation, the solution principles developed together, even if preliminary and imperfect, can serve as useful counterfactuals. In some cases, their contribution may lead to questioning the scientific foundations and other elements of the knowledge base used by the researcher-innovator that were previously taken for granted.

In terms of the support that can be delivered to innovators in the future, it is possible to draw some important intermediary conclusions. Citizen engagement may deliver important insights about alternative solutions to a societal issue they are confronted with. But it needs to be complement by incorporating additional knowledge from different disciplines. Citizens hold a particular characteristic: they have no scientific or fields constraints. They are in a position to think and ask questions that require integrating several scientific disciplines. Due to the limited time available, citizens participating in the workshops missed in their reflections the potential connection between the solutions and positive externalities. So, new foods, or new solutions to nutrition, may not only have positive impacts on citizens health but also on the environment (depending on the solution envisioned) yet, this is not mentioned in their reflections, but in the interpretation of the data that is carried out afterward. Complementary, they are mentioning some potential negative externalities, but they remain quite general.

The follow up of the UCLouvain pilot will articulate the following activities:

- Internal diffusion of results inside the university to inform all the actors of the university that supported the experimental approach to citizen engagement.
- Internal discussion about developing theses and teaching related to circular economy and civil society engagement in innovation.
- Diffusion of result to the participants of the pilot before discussion through a micro-platform dedicated to them where results will be first popularized and then key aspects of the report will be commented.
- Open4S lunch seminars where participants will be invited to exchange with PhD students presenting related research and where they will learn about key scientific aspects, diffusion online will be available to avoid travel costs.
- Agenda shaping to support the development of a project funded by a regional agency for circular food innovation inside and outside the BCR.

The assessment of the potential need for innovation and its societal impact through citizen consultation is an important aspect of responsible research and innovation (RRI). Such consultations not only help familiarize scientists and innovators with the benefits of involving citizens in innovation processes, but also provide valuable insight into the contribution of such processes within regional RRI frameworks, which is particularly important in the context of the TRANSFORM project. Therefore, it is crucial to evaluate the role of citizen consultations in promoting RRI at the regional level, and their potential impact on the development of socially responsible and sustainable innovation practices.

As described in D5.1, the R&I financed by Innoviris lacks of funding mechanisms that support the involvement of civil society (apart for specific case of funding programmes such as Co-Create).

4. Impact

4.1 Impacts of the TRANSFORM processes in policy-making

To understand the impact of a project like TRANSFORM on an administration like Innoviris, we need to distinguish two trajectories, which inevitably intertwine and resonate with each other. On the one hand, we have the administration's process and, on the other, the maturation process of an innovation.

For Innoviris, the process is partly based on the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) of the region, which frames part of our activities. The Brussels RIS3 (Research and Innovation Smart Specialisation Strategy) is embedded within the guidelines of the regional innovation plan that gives us a thematic framework for part of our activities. The process of drafting the S3 used citizen participation to validate certain trends or refine the thematic orientations. However, this was done outside the TRANSFORM project for timing reasons. In this consultation process, the citizen consultation came relatively late, and built on existing top-down work. Thanks to this RIS3, we have a framework for developing calls for projects in the strategic innovation areas of the RIS3, similar to the mission approach advocated by Horizon Europe.

As stated by BE participation asbl (the pilot and cluster leader, the aim of the unsold food pilot (within the framework of the TRANSFORM project) was 1) to test a tool, which consisted of a participatory process bringing together quadruple-helix stakeholders, to be used in the future by public administrations supporting R&I and 2) to showcase the added value for public administrations supporting R&I to perform similar activities in the future, which allow to achieve a deeper understanding of the R&I ecosystem beyond its typical actors (the academia and the private sector), and therefore better address societal needs while avoiding potential adverse impacts of R&I.

Innoviris finds it interesting to also observe whether such type of processes can also lead to the emergence of a relevant theme for a call for research and innovation projects. According to Innoviris part of the challenge was, without (too much) guiding the citizen in their discussions and debates, to know if it is possible through this methodology to bring out knowledge needs – event though this aim was never explicitly mentioned to the pilot leader

nor to the participants. Innoviris is therefore interested to see whether these needs can be translated into research questions, requiring either an innovation approach to provide a solution to the problem, or a more academic research to bring out the facts necessary to support a science-based policy.

To do this, the chosen case study was particularly divisive, with interesting tensions for the public authorities. Indeed, in this pilot, the starting point was the launch of an economic activity around unsold food, with the idea of minimising the environmental impact of our food. While this is an interesting approach, economic initiatives such as Too Good to Go have failed to assess the social impact of their solution. By launching these economic initiatives, part of the flow, which was originally captured by social actors to provide food aid to the poor, has been diverted to these new actors. This part of the flow, to be saleable, is moreover the most qualitative. As a result, social aid associations must deal with lower quality and smaller flows.

This pilot helped Innoviris to structure its thinking, which was already underway internally, around measuring the social and environmental impacts of its projects. The tension between the different impacts is not new, but it was often based on the difficulty of having an economic impact versus social and environmental impacts. Trying to assess the different impacts in Innoviris' programmes today remains still complex. The use of a participatory process to do a 360° scan of the impacts of a project is very powerful. However, this is unfortunately not feasible for most of Innoviris' grants, as the amounts of money involved do not justify such a dynamic. By way of comparison, Innoviris already has a minor form of citizen participation in the evaluation of some of its projects, with citizens present in the evaluation juries of the Cocrete call. While Innoviris accepts the extra work that this represents in terms of the benefits for both Innoviris and the project leaders, unfortunately it is only possible for specific types of projects. And it cannot be extrapolated to all its grants.

But such a process has the power to make emerge other important needs. The knowledge needs. Within the unsold food pilot workshops, it appears to Innoviris that such an important theme needs more information, to go further than the basic and probably false "I have heard that...".

This is all the more important as the process that was carried out within the framework of the pilot is the first step of a policy process that would have led to a co-development (quadruple-helix based) initiative including citizens, around the issue/tension of unsold food

and social help. The second step, the co-development part, was way beyond the scope of the TRANSFORM project, and the competencies of Innoviris. Innoviris' main concern was therefore limited by its role within the region. And this case was for Innoviris the opportunity to try a new way to address societal challenges with citizens.

As previously mentioned, for Innoviris, actual participatory processes are mainly reaction processes where it asks to citizen to massively analyze and validate top-down propositions. According to Innoviris, a secondary objective of this pilot was to find out whether such a purely bottom-up approach would lead to the definition of call topics as qualitatively as with more top-down approaches. And if the citizens involved in these dynamics would find meaning in the solutions that could emerge from future R&I processes. In this respect, and given the temporality of R&I, this possibility will be well outside the scope of the TRANSFORM project. As we have seen, according to Innoviris the participatory approach was to allow the discussion to be structured quite freely towards specific objectives to solve the situation, in order to measure whether R&I-related needs could emerge. The main benefit according to Innoviris was to bring an ecosystem to the table and to bring out a whole set of institutional obstacles to a fair distribution of these waste flows. As a result, for Innoviris the main observation of these workshops is the difficulty of the participants, from all backgrounds, to take a step back and gain perspective on the issue by themselves. The solutions proposed often remain in the realm of action and funding requests. According to Innoviris, this is linked both to the theme and to the political context surrounding this theme. Nevertheless, according to Innoviris this is a very powerful methodology to make a mapping of an ecosystem and to determine the – types of - relations between actors. Interdependences are often sociotechnical locking elements that inhibit progress. In a context of innovation, it could also be a good starting point for more top-down projects or studies.

Nevertheless, when re-using this methodology, according to Innoviris it is important in the workshop approach to help participants leave the operational context and to get them to dream their ideal solution. When tried, a few interesting ideas/propositions emerged for the discussions. According to Innoviris, this approach helps to bring out non-existent needs and solutions. And it shows how information is needed to make such an initiative a success.

Therefore, according to Innoviris the process tested in the unsold food pilot is very pertinent within a context of the preparation of co-development of a solution with the citizens, leading rapidly to the public action but shows some limits in the context of making emerge research thematic.

As mentioned at the beginning of the chapter, there are two intertwined trajectories in Innoviris' activities. Its innovation grants, which are partly based on its S3, are grafted along the innovation chain, within the framework of the GBER. Ideally, the challenge is to give the necessary but sufficient support. With this in mind, Innoviris has been trying for some years to adopt the makers' credo: Fail fast fail cheap. Therefore, Innoviris is looking for instruments that allow it to highlight as quickly as possible when an innovation reaches a dead end and funding has to be stopped.

a.2 Uptake of the “AquaSens” and “Algorella” processes in policy-making

As part of the pilots “AquaSens” and “Algorella”, citizen consultation was used in the evaluation of the potential of future innovations. According to UCLouvain, the objective was to test these approaches to see if they could obtain feedback that would allow them to go beyond purely “customer assessment” methodologies and explore the social and/or environmental externalities of an innovation with citizens. The “AquaSens” pilot allowed them to start thinking about the potential of such a dynamic, without however going all the way, as it was a “pilot of the pilots”, therefore a preliminary test activity. With the “Algorella” pilot, UCLouvain was able to explore “different participation configurations”, enabling them to obtain optimal feedback on the added value of citizen engagement for impacts assessment of an innovation and, above all, which was not necessarily the intention at the outset, on ways of improving the innovation in terms of its social and environmental impacts.

Innoviris considers this tool to be particularly suitable, especially for innovation processes within the academic world where project leaders may lack the necessary experience to take impacts into account. Innoviris has already communicated to the research support departments of various regional academic players that it is willing to accept expenses related to consultation processes in subsidies that concern the valorisation of academic research results. The question of transposing this possibility to private research projects is more delicate but still very relevant. Innoviris already assess the environmental and social impacts of these projects during the ex-ante process. And the legal text governing support for private projects is currently being revised, with the future introduction of the requirement to justify positive environmental and social impacts. The advantage of doing this before the creation of a spin-off is that the newly created company will be directly eligible for future regional subsidies for companies. This will increase their chances and facilitate innovation processes in the region.

4.2 Links with S3

The new European framework for innovation policy postulates that research and innovation should contribute to social, climate, and economic progress. This shift in approach is at the heart of the European Green Deal, the framework for the development of all European Commission support and funding programmes, which triggers a range of important initiatives affecting regional, industrial, and innovation policies. This new framework puts climate objectives on the same level as economic and social objectives for the first time and aims to achieve them in a coherent way. This focus on societal challenges and impacts is also operationalized in the 'mission-oriented' approach that has been adopted in the new European research and innovation framework programme Horizon Europe 2021-2027, which succeeds Horizon 2020. Important new European initiatives and investments in, for example, the circular economy, the bioeconomy or digitalization (digital transition) also explicitly link the strengthening of competitiveness with the achievement of climate objectives.

The approach adopted for the development of the new Brussels RIS3 is in line with this trend and is explicitly demand-driven. The development process, therefore, starts with the identification of the region's main challenges and the societal needs of its citizens and links them to the potential of the Brussels research and innovation ecosystem. The intersection between these challenges and the research and innovation potential leads to the identification of new strategic innovation areas (SIAs). These form coherent sets of activities around which to mobilize regional RDI, its investments, and its knowledge capital to contribute to a number of socio-economic transitions.

The regional R&I policy priorities are articulated under four main headings linked to the economic, societal, ecological and social transitions are central to the political strategies. The priorities of economic development and innovation are at the service of these transitions and aim to achieve them.

The ecological transition towards a zero-carbon region focuses on strategies and activities to mitigate the impacts of climate change, as well as better resource and waste management. These orientations focus strongly on the energy transition including renewable energies, smart grids, low-carbon production, and green mobility, as well as on the circular economy, low tech, and recycling, reuse, and repair technologies.

The social transition guaranteeing the conditions for a dignified life aims to fight social exclusion, reduce the poverty rate and wage and sub-regional inequalities, increase the employment rate and the quality of jobs, accessible and safe housing and public green space for all, minimize the consequences of the digital divide, and ensure better health and well-being for all. The contributions of the innovation policy will be fed into this transition by a better activation of social innovations and "responsible research and innovation", by the adequacy of spatial planning that takes into account the mechanisms of diffusion, multiplication, and spatial valorization of innovations, of new infrastructures and methods of learning and training, of new approaches and technologies of care and biomedicine.

Economic and innovation policies and strategies are put at the service of social and ecological transitions, aiming at a sustainable, resilient, and inclusive economy. The main levers will be a strengthening of the productive capacity in the Region to compensate for the permanent de-industrialization and the acceleration of the digital transformation of enterprises.

In a collaborative and inclusive spirit, the development of the new RIS3 and the RIP 2021-2027 have included a broad consultative component. It mobilizes the known players in the Brussels innovation system (triple helix), but also new players who are less visible in this system (quadruple helix). This consultation allows for a detailed understanding of the specificities of the Brussels terrain and ensures the selection of SIAs that are deeply rooted in the wider RDI ecosystem.

By combining the global generic issues and challenges with the current political priorities and strategies in the CBR, six societal challenges have been identified as particularly relevant for Brussels: Climate & Energy ; Resource optimization ; Mobility ; Healthy & sustainable food ; Health & well-being ; Participative & inclusive society.

The intersection of these societal challenges and the strengths of the Brussels RDI ecosystem leads to the identification of Strategic Innovation Area (SIAs). To focus Brussels' strengths towards more prosperity, resilience, sustainability and well-being, the Brussels RIS3 is structured according to 1 transversal SID and 5 thematic SID.

The transversal SID should be considered as a key factor of this Innovation Regional Plan, critical to the thematic SID. It has its own place in the RIS3: Advanced digital technologies & services.

The 5 thematic SID identified all represent innovation opportunities for the economic development of the CBR, with a concrete potential to contribute to the answers to societal challenges. They have been defined in such a way as to present a maximum of coherence within them in terms of the innovative activities they should stimulate, while maximizing cross-fertilization between fields, technologies, disciplines, and actors. After multiple participative processes, they have been redefined as: Resilient Buildings & Infrastructures; Optimal Resource Use; Efficient and sustainable urban flows for inclusive urban space management ; Health & Personalized and Integrated Care ; Social innovation, public innovation and social inclusion.

As mentioned previously, RRI has been identified as a key lever to operate social transition withing the region. Therefore, the TRANSFORM project fit perfectly with Innoviris' S3 strategy. Moreover, the choice of the Brussels's cluster to address challenges correlated to circular economy fit perfectly with the SIA "Optimal Resource Use". The "Algorella" pilot has been used to help a project with its impacts, using a consultation process to exploit citizens to collect feedback regarding social and environmental challenges. This is undoubtedly a demand-driven (re)-orientation of a research process, which is also promoted by the new orientation of Innoviris innovation regional plan, and by extension by its S3.

4.3 Medium and long-term impacts of TRANSFORM for stronger territorial RRI in the Brussels-Capital region

As mentioned previously, Innoviris is currently busy with the rewriting of its legal constitutive texts with the objective that all the subsidized projects should be environmentally and socially exemplary. And TRANSFORM helped Innoviris to choose between the different scenarios it had in mind. It means that Innoviris will have to evaluate the social, environmental, eco-systemic impacts of each project. Therefore, Innoviris can say that at short to medium terms all the subsidized projects will fit in a RRI approach. Moreover, the design of its future call of proposal will be constructed with the same idea of impacts and a "Do not significantly Harm" strategy that was highlighted by TRANSFORM. It means for example that an environmental call could not lead to a negative social impact, whatever the foreseen environmental benefits.

5. Practical guidelines

5.1 *The added value for policy makers*¹⁶

Processes such as those of the TRANSFORM pilots will assist public administration in identifying blind spots in public policy. Innoviris has learned that instead of highlighting thematic missions, it is more effective to help administrations find the right questions and information needs to establish the best focus for a funding thematic call. Additionally, mapping an ecosystem and understanding interdependencies and sociotechnical locking elements is valuable when designing a call for proposal aimed at addressing ecosystemic problems. Conducting this mapping exercise prior to designing the call can assist any administration in better designing the evaluation process to identify projects that fail to consider sociotechnical locking mechanisms..

In this case, it was difficult to find an angle for the unsold food ecosystem, because the tension between economic, environmental, and social impact aren't totally correlated. The economic activities and environmental implications are more related to overproduction and waste of food. The social situation is more complex, and the need of food urgency aid is the consequence of a more systemic and complex situation linked to poverty and social justice. These two systemic problems collide here, and it is not possible to address both challenges at the same time, even for experts. Innoviris was not expecting citizens to find a solution. But the group helps Innoviris to map the system and make emerge the needed information to assess the situation: quantities, mapping of the flux, legal framework lock-in effects, sociotechnical locking mechanisms... All these data would be needed to address a response to the confrontation and to find a science-based solution, using prospective methodologies.

Moreover, according to Innoviris it is very difficult to make 360° assessments of projects, especially if it is only one person that assess a project. It will help also to have a pragmatic evaluation of a project, from people that have no benefit of the funding of the project. The closer to the market the project is, the most relevant this kind of citizen assessment will be. It can help small funding administrations to not fall in the trap of sunk costs fallacy (“we have funded this idea since a long time, we need to do it again until it goes to the market”).

¹⁶ This section was written by Jérémy Levin, Cédric Verstraete (Innoviris)

Sooner we can stop unnecessary projects, more money will be injected to high potential high impact projects.

5.2 The added value for researchers and innovators¹⁷

In a Quadruple Helix configuration, modifying research and innovation in a direction that would be more "responsible" (with regard to societal issues) can be done in different ways. The choice of general orientations for a public policy and public support for innovation in a given territory is a classic lever, the preparation of research programs and more precise calls for projects, operationalizing the general orientations is another. This makes it possible to instill a better consideration of collective or societal objectives. By conditioning the financing of a project on the respect of a certain number of conditions - some of which relate to the resolution of legitimate issues - one gives "incentives" to develop certain types of knowledge and push their development in product innovation or process innovation, in directions that are considered as desirable from the point of view of society as a whole. A "bottom-up" construction dynamic of general orientations, or of programs or of calls for projects (etc.) based on citizens engagement will enable informed choices, better programs and calls, will improve their legitimacy and the effectiveness of public policies (well-known examples¹⁸ are informed citizen recommendations on policy questions, citizen opinion on policy questions, ad hoc or institutionalized Citizens' juries panels, et.). A key condition is that this dynamic must be carried out according to rigorous protocols, reinforcing both the exploration of possibilities and the legitimacy of the choices made. The changes observed then are particularly interesting¹⁹.

UCLouvain has experimented a well-known citizen consultation approach in ongoing research oriented towards product innovation for the Circular Economy. The methodology approach used, to which the UCLouvain team has given the name of "XLAB", is particularly adapted to a setting corresponding to an ongoing research process within a university.

¹⁷ This section was written by Ignace Adant, Joaquin Landazuri Benitez (UCLouvain)

¹⁸ See Česnulaitytė, I. (2020), "Models of representative deliberative processes", in Innovative Citizen Participation and New Democratic Institutions: Catching the Deliberative Wave, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/36f3f279-en>.

¹⁹ See a.o. : Massey, Beth & Verma, Piyush & Khadem, Md. Shafiuzzaman Khan. (2018). Citizen Engagement as a Business Model for Smart Energy Communities. 1-6. 10.1109/EFEA.2018.8617063.

Observations and analyses have been carried out by UCLouvain team members at two levels. Analyzing the exchanges between an innovator and a group of citizens, and collecting feedback and reflections on the methodology used. Following this, the UCLouvain team has reflected on what is the meaning and relevance of such type of processes for the key regional actors of the Brussels cluster, Innoviris, and how this can impact the way they support R&I at regional level. “Aglorella” is an exemplary case of a future Healthy Circular Food. The experimental citizen engagement process in research has generated knowledge that the innovators do not have otherwise, related to the constraints faced by the citizen when they look for solution at individuals problems (diet and deficiencies) and for collective stakes (animal welfare and environment). It stresses also how difficult it is for participants to solve both type of problems at the same time. Simultaneous recommendations on food and on environmental issues are likely to create tensions that citizens are not necessarily able to resolve. An innovation can be assessed by its ability to resolve these tensions. Hence an interesting contribution for a better impact assessment approach – based on citizen engagement - of circular food innovation. This type of processes had not been tested before within UCLouvain R&I activities.

Researchers-innovators at university are not the only one to benefit from this form of knowledge intermediation. The public authority in charge of innovation, if it is included in dynamics for knowledge creation, could observe transparently the work of defining the PBSDs (problems-needs-solutions-demands) and also the choices made for the evaluation of the impacts by the innovator(s). This would stave off questions - and mistrust – about the merits of innovations. But this can also trigger a learning process, which is useful to allow better evaluations of projects submitted. Better assessment of the quality of analyses supplied by innovators and of ex-ante impacts assessment reduces differential of expertise.

Far from being limited to this passive posture, the public authority could also actively participate in the intermediation mechanism by relaying the orientations that have been discussed and validated elsewhere with citizens (and in particular in processes that it directly pilots, see public lever in the typology above). The expected effects are an increased finesse of the results, better learning and a strengthening of the legitimacy of the entire analysis in a Spheres-type device. When the evaluation of the impacts of a project is done 'in house' at the university or when it is done solely by the public authority (innovation agency) which chooses the projects to be funded, there is no shared learning of this type, nor reinforcement of the results.

Finally, it should be noted that there is a similar process for impact assessment (with members of the Quadruple Helix) realized in certain calls for tenders for international cooperation projects. This gives rise to the formulation of projects in two phases, with intermediate funding aimed at covering the expenses necessary for the deepening, on the ground, of certain aspects of the project, including the evaluation of the impacts with the stakeholders.

Even if the experience presented here is imperfect and is limited, one can already see how the three roles played by university can benefit citizen engagement in research and innovation processes at university. The university has three roles: teaching/training, research and service to society. The third role has, depending on the case and the place, been called into question because it was reduced to the commercialization of innovations or because it was difficult to identify the positive effect of research for society as a whole. The Algorella innovation is an exemplary case where the impact for university and for society is quite clearly identifiable. A modification introduced in the way of fulfilling the second role of university (research) can lead to even more significant impacts for its third role, that of service to Society. And it's not round. Indeed, the first role is not ignored either. We emphasized at the beginning of the report that the innovation studied here took place in a very specific context, where researchers and students interact. In this particular context, a mechanism for citizen engagement such the one developed here (called Spheres in previous task) will allow M.A. students to become familiar with citizen engagement and contribute to put lessons into practice. In the case of the Algorella, it is easy to see that the analysis requires better support on disciplines or even rethinking the lessons provided for certain disciplines so that they can be mobilized for this purpose.

5.3 Institutional changes to implement lessons learned within the AquaSens and Algorella pilots²⁰

The analysis of the two pilots that focused on engaging citizens in early research and innovation processes at the university ("AquaSens" and "Algorella"), highlighted the benefits that research at university can find through the application of carefully chosen "SPHERES" protocols. Although these results still need to be reviewed, shared, and enriched by further

²⁰ Chapter written by Ignace Adant and Joaquin Landazuri, UCLouvain.

research, it is already possible to identify several institutional changes that could support the use of participatory approaches in research at the university.

An additional change to the introduction of citizen engagement processes in research and innovation is the development of transdisciplinary research. Transdisciplinary research is precisely a collaborative process between the Quadruple Helix (QH) and across academic disciplines where each stakeholder brings diverse perspectives and expertise to the research process. It relies on an iterative and reflexive approach to research, where the questions, methods, and outcomes are constantly re-evaluated through impacts evaluation, refined based on feedback from all stakeholders and a sustainable learning dynamic established between discovering the complex picture of a societal problem and the scientific work on a limited set of problem and causalities to understand (see our narrative at section 1).

UCLouvain has made transdisciplinary research one of the pillars of its Transition Plan, reflecting the university's commitment to creating a more sustainable and responsible future for itself and for society as a whole. This has translated notably into the choice of new ways of working in M.A. and PhD theses, where the contributions of different disciplines are articulated on common questions and fields, and where impact evaluation methodologies are gradually being developed (for example, Hauwaert 2019 , Leclercq 2020 , Lebrun et al. 2021 , to name only researchers who, in addition to their research work, voluntarily participated in the TRANSFORM pilots).

The work on pilots in the TRANSFORM framework, particularly on the protocols required to transform a Design Thinking approach into an approach aimed at gradually defining and evaluating innovation, extends beyond TRANSFORM itself. This methodology has been applied in international projects to assess innovative solutions related to water expertise. The appeal of this approach lies not only in its scientific work (examining the contribution of diverse populations or civil societies to R&I) but also in its ability to maintain a reflective dynamic in long-term projects. By doing so, one can develop long-term research dynamics that internalize the multi-stakeholder approach of "Algorella" for social and technological innovations to be implemented in contexts where conditions for teaching and innovation are less favourable than in the Brussels Capital Region.

However, progress is still insufficient and will require additional efforts. Work on the Circular Economy is a good example: this requires going beyond preconceived ideas (associating waste with food), finding new causalities (modifying the container-content links in the

circular economy of food packaging), and breaking down and articulating research and teachings belonging to different programs. The circular economy is not simply an additional aspect of the analysis of agri-food systems or of the study of ICT (for example); it is a more complex vision that demands different teaching and research practices. In other words, it requires rethinking the three roles the university and their articulation.

The development of transdisciplinary research requires additional changes within the university, in its networks, and beyond. Within the university, the evaluation of dissertations and theses must be organized accordingly, as well as the recognition of high-quality work through prizes and scholarships, which is still not common enough.

It is also important to be able to find collaborators outside the university, through strong mobility during PhD and in international networks bringing together multiple universities coordinated around common themes (see, for example, Circle U). The reason is simple: it increases the probability of finding complementary research and builds on open QHs that are open to actors outside of a given region or territory. Strong support for these networks in their transdisciplinary approach, particularly in relation to the circular economy, would be particularly useful, and access to funding remains a key issue in any case.

Financial support for research on the role of stakeholder engagement in innovation dynamics and on the roles of original forms of intermediation necessary for this should be strengthened. This includes original experimental approaches such as that initiated with Aglorella. It will contribute to strengthening a key research effort that questions the role of civil society in innovation (beyond the classical vision of the state) for sustainable development and the transition. With and for the European citizens.

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